

D2.5 - Implementation of Identified Health & Safety Requirements

WP 2, T 2.5

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Executive summary

This document is the deliverable “D2.5 – Implementation of Identified Health & Safety Requirements” of the eLITHE project (project reference: 101138325).

In the eLITHE project, as defined in the proposal, SGS is the leader off the **Task 2.5. - Implementation of identified health & safety requirements.**

The eLITHE Project aims to support the electrification of the ceramic industries, across three different processes and will be demonstrated at 3 different pilot sites at relevant scale:

1. TORRECID: A ceramic frits smelter (1,100- 1,500°C) combining induction and resistive heating through electrodes.
2. MYTILINEOS: A microwave-based calcination furnace (1,200°C) for the calcination of alumina.
3. IZF: A tunnel kiln (1,100°C) combining radiant walls and flexible hybrid burners for bricks and tiles firing.

The goal is to develop highly efficient and safe electric high temperature heating processes that replace fossil-based heating systems in the industrial ceramic sector.

The objective of this deliverable is to analyze the electrification of the ceramic industries of the three pilot sites – Torrecid, METLEN and IZF – from a Health and Safety (H&S) perspective, focusing on the H&S risks and preventive measures – technical, engineering, and organizational.

To comply with this objective, this deliverable develops the following documents:

1. Gap Analysis

The first activity of this task is to conduct a **gap analysis to identify areas where current processes and products do not meet health and safety requirements**, considering the specific challenges of the electrification process.

Based on the Gap Analysis, it will be essential to identify the main compliances requirements to develop safe and compliant solutions. These compliances should cover both products and processes, including the use of appropriate materials, equipment, and control systems.

The Referred Gap Analysis was based on the preparation of a checklist result of the Kiln risk analysis, distributed to all Demos Sites.

According to the responses from Demos Sites, the only identified GAPS were the absence of PTW (Permit to Work Procedure) and LOTO (Lock-Out TAG-Out) procedures.

2. Procedures development resulting from the Gap analysis:

- 2.1. **Design Safety Philosophy** – This document defines and establishes the minimum requirements for the design and engineering of the safety systems required to eliminate, prevent, control or mitigate the plant hazards;
- 2.2. **Human Factor Engineering (HFE) Philosophy** – This document defines the principles focus on respecting the individual and social integrity of workers, on creating safe and healthy workspaces;
- 2.3. **Permit to Work (PTW) Procedure** – A permit to work can be considered as a specialised Safe System of Work under which certain high risk activities may only be carried out with specific permission of the Authorised Person;
- 2.4. **Lock-Out /TAG-Out (LOTO) Procedure** – this is a specific procedure to prevent the unexpected energization, start-up or release of stored energy that may result in bodily injury or property damage during construction, testing, maintenance and servicing of machinery or equipment by ISOLATION (Lockout/Tag out (LOTO) of that part of the installations that is related to a specified hazardous job activity.

Documents 2.1 and 2.2 are necessary to consider in the design phase and documents 2.3 and 2.4 will be necessary in the commissioning, use and maintenance phases of the installation.

Beyond this project development phase, SGS's task will continue in the implementation phase with all these work packages (W4-W6), which will consider a final engineering stage to integrate the solutions in the current processes, commissioning and demonstration campaigns in real industrial sites.

The delivery of this deliverable is done in accordance with the description in the Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A with 1 month time deviation and no content deviation from the original planning apart from the pending procedures that require the full design of 3 pilot sites.

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1 GAP ANALYSIS

1.1 Introduction

The first activity of this task is to conduct a gap analysis to identify areas where current processes and products do not meet health and safety requirements, considering the specific challenges of the electrification process.

Based on the **Gap Analysis**, it will be essential to identify the main compliance requirements to develop safe and compliant solutions. These compliances should cover both products and processes, including the use of appropriate materials, equipment, and control systems.

Following this, the **Health and Safety Requirements** will be defined, considering the risks associated with the electrification process, such as electrical hazards, high temperature hazards, fire hazards, and chemical exposure, specifically related to the Kiln.

Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) will be specified, and a pipeline of work will be established to ensure that workers have the necessary equipment and training to perform their jobs safely.

Finally, it will be ensured that the identified health and safety requirements are implemented and enforced throughout the process, considering regular inspections and training sessions that can help maintain compliance and prevent accidents.

Table 1: Acronym List – Gap Analysis

Acronym	Definition
LOTO	Lock-out Tag-out
PTW	Permit to Work
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
ALARP	As Low as Reasonable Possible
HFE	Human Factor Engineering

1.2 Process Overview

To identify the requirements for preventive measures, a risk analysis related to a kiln of the type used in each pilot plant, was carried out. In this way, were identified the risks, based on equipment, products, and operations as well as existing types of energy, and the respective preventive and control measures necessary to control these risks, considering the current state of the art in health and safety knowledge in industrial facilities.

The safety requirements have been represented in a safety control/preventive requirements table wish were sent to all the demos, based in that risk analysis of the new processes, considering the three pilot plants, as follows:

Pilot site 1 (P1): Ceramic frits melting (TCID)

Current Process - fossil heating energy based	New Process - electric heating melting solution
<u>Description:</u> TCID current smelters are continuous furnaces Involved electricity and natural gas.	<u>Description:</u> The design of the furnace will be based on the combination of heat transfer through induction and electrodes heating.
<u>Major Risks:</u> High temperature, chemical, fire, explosion, electrocution.	<u>Major Risks:</u> High temperature, chemical, fire, electrocution.

Pilot site 2 (P2): alumina calcination (MYT)

Current Process - fossil heating energy based	New Process - electric heating melting solution
<u>Description:</u> MYT currently owns two vertical alumina calciners, based in consumption of natural gas.	<u>Description:</u> The design will be based on all-electric microwave-based for alumina calcination, implementing a new microwave furnace.
<u>Major Risks:</u> High temperature, chemical, fire, explosion.	<u>Major Risks:</u> High temperature, chemical, fire, electrocution.

Pilot site 3: Brick firing (IZF)

Current Process - fossil heating energy based	New Process - hybrid system based on electrically solution
<p><u>Description:</u> IZF currently owns large chamber kiln, based in consumption of methane gas (CH₄).</p> <p><u>Major Risks:</u> High temperature, chemical, fire, explosion.</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> The design will be based on hybrid system based on electrically (heat transfer done by radiation screens installed in the furnace walls) / Hybrid heating with NG and green H₂</p> <p><u>Major Risks:</u> High temperature, chemical, fire, explosion, electrocution.</p>

All the demos responded, as follows:

- **Torreacid:** LOTO procedure and Permit to Work (PTW) Procedure, were missing.
- **IZF:** LOTO procedure and Permit to Work (PTW) Procedure, were missing.
- **METLEN:** all the requirements are implemented.

The referred table based in a risk assessment is presented in the chapter 5. ANNEXES – 5.1.

1.3 Gap Analysis philosophy

The “Controls in Place”, also named as preventive measures, as identified considering the following kind of measures:

- Organizational
- Engineering and technical
- PPE`s

The GAP analysis philosophy could be explained using the “Swiss Cheese” theory, devised by Reason (1997) – which is a generic model of accident causation. Known as the ‘Swiss cheese’ model, it is depicted in Figure 1. Although not specific to the construction industry, this model it has provided a key reference point for construction industry accident causation models. The strength of Reason’s model is that it reveals how accidents occur through the combined effect of organizational, local workplace and individual factors.

Reason’s systems-based helps analyze how human error is induced by organizational factors such as:

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- workplaces or systems design
- budget allocation
- communication
- planning
- scheduling, and
- unwritten rules about acceptable practices within the company.

Workplace accidents can be traced back to these organizational and workplace factors, which Reason refers to as 'latent condition pathways'. The pathway is an alignment of gaps or holes in organizational systems. Cumulatively, these gaps create the conditions for adverse safety outcomes. Circumstances which may result in accidents in local workplaces, such as construction sites, can arise because of management practices, priorities and decisions that lead to unrealistic work schedules, poor maintenance, under staffing, low pay, inadequate supervisor-to-worker ratios, ambiguous or impractical procedures, or unpractical goals.

These latent conditions interact with human behavior – such as cutting corners or prioritizing the delivery of materials over an adhering to safe work practices – resulting in human error.

Reason suggests that while many unsafe acts occur, **only some unsafe acts result in accidents because systems have built-in defenses.**

It is when these defenses fail that organizational accidents occur.

Figure 1: 'Swiss cheese' accident causation model (Reason, 1997).

Inspired by this model, this deliverable should incorporate all the additional defenses, based on Risk Analysis, to ensure that the risk level at the site aligns with the As Low As Reasonable Possible (ALARP) principle.

Figure 2: ALARP principle.

2 DELIVERED PROCEDURES

2.1 Design Safety Philosophy

2.1.1 Introduction

Safety in design forms an integral component of European H&S policy and legislation. All state and territory H&S legislation requires some form of systematic approach to managing H&S risks associated with the design of structures (as well as plant and materials). Codes of practice provide risk management processes to help duty holders comply with these statutory requirements.

The legislation establishes detailed requirements for managing safety in design with an emphasis on integrating safety considerations into project team decision making. For instance, mandates the appointment of a professional Project Health and Safety Coordinator. Evidence suggests Directive 92/57/EEC of 24 June 1992, has contributed to cultural shift in the European construction industry about safety in design, although this Directive is still often viewed as a 'paper based' exercise.

Design Safety Philosophy takes in account that, safe design is an important step in ensuring that a product is free from health and safety risks, considering:

a) Managing Risks in Designing Plant

When designing plant, consider:

- all the phases in its lifecycle, including manufacture, use, dismantling and disposal.
- how someone can erect and install it safely.
- how someone should use it, or how they might misuse it.
- maintaining and repairing it.
- In case of failure, how to resolve the problem safely.

To make sure plant is safe to use, also consider:

- users' physical abilities
- how many tasks the user can perform at a time
- the layout of the area where the plant will be used.

b) Managing Risks from the Start

Identify, assess, and control hazards from the start. It's better to design a product:

- without hazards
- with the right risk control measures included, if the product might need them at simultaneously – for example, safety equipment like seatbelts or fall protection.

This document defines and establishes the minimum requirements for the design and engineering of the **safety systems required to eliminate, prevent, control or mitigate hazards associated with the electrification of ceramic industries** at the three pilot sites (Torrecid, METLEN and IZF).

Safe design is the method of ensuring the health and safety of individuals who will interact with a product throughout its entire lifetime. It encompasses not only those who will operate the product, but also those who will assemble, clean, maintain, repair, and dispose it. A designer must consider potential risks and work to mitigate them during the entire design phase through careful decisions about materials, manufacturing processes, methods of use, intended disposal practices, and additional safety features - whether required by law or not.

The emphasis is on achieving safety through good design, rather than relying on procedures and protective equipment.

The benefits of Safe Design are summarized in the following figure:

Figure 3: Benefits of safe design.

Safety in design is managed through a process of staged design and constructability reviews that become increasingly more fine-grained. For example, H&S risks should be analyzed in more detail as the design work progresses. Typically:

- a risk assessment protocol is established at the proposal development stage.
- a preliminary risk review is undertaken, and a risk register is established, at the concept design stage.
- further and progressively more detailed safety-in-design reviews occur at the concept and detailed design stages, and
- a final review of design-related H&S risks takes place at the construction document development stage (when detailed design is 'frozen').

This systematic approach to managing safety-in-design, undoubtedly increases the consistency and reliability of safety in design activities when applied across projects.

There is widespread recognition that safety-in-design reviews must involve people with knowledge and experience in the construction and maintenance of the facilities being designed.

In this context, integrating mechanisms are needed to ensure that communication flows are free and open, and that people with the correct mix of knowledge and experience are engaged in safety-in-design reviews.

Table 2: Acronym List – Design Safety Philosophy.

Acronym	Definition
MCP	Manual call points
NFPA	National Fire Protection Association
OSHA	Occupational safety and Health Administration
SDS	Safety Data Sheet
EU	European Union

2.1.2 Materials Hazards

Some of the most relevant potential hazards associated with the materials and equipment used in the plant can be highlighted such as:

- Injury to personnel because of contact with:

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- **High temperature** - Kiln surface can be extremely hot: up to 260°C (500°F). Workers can be severely burned if they touch the hot surface.
- **Electricity** - In the kiln, electrical hazards can be fatal. It is important to follow the same systematic approach used for other health and safety issues when dealing with electrical safety.
- **Chemicals such as silicas** - long term exposure to silica dust could cause lung damage.

2.1.3 Equipment and Plant Layout

Layout principles

Plot Plan development shall follow the following codes and standards:

- Plot Plan requirements and equipment spacing shall conform to local regulations, supplemented with guidelines by XL "GAPS" (Global Asset Protection Services), and the API, IEC, and NFPA codes. The latest editions of these documents shall be used, unless otherwise indicated.
- Process unit spacing is required to minimize risks due to turnaround maintenance activities in a unit while adjacent units remain in service. Equipment spacing shall be in accordance with PNE00003 and GAP.2.5.2. A.

When designing the facilities, the following layout principles shall be considered:

- Provide sufficient separation between equipment and services handling potentially flammable materials and the plant boundary or public areas to minimize injury and escalation potential.
- Consider the prevailing wind directions and site topography for movement and dispersion of spilled flammable, dust, and smoke releases.
- Adequate separation between hazardous areas and emergency services, main safety equipment, escape routes and areas considered non-hazardous.
- Control facilities and related buildings shall be preferentially located so that they are largely unaffected by heat radiation resulting in severe accidents. Where this cannot be achieved, construction of buildings shall be sufficient to withstand the effects of accidental loads.
- Adequate maintenance and access to all areas for firefighting and associated vehicles.
- Provide access/escape routes to and from all areas of the facility.
- Reduce operators working in the facility exposed to hazardous materials.
- Reduce truck movements on site, also check front-end loaders and other mobile equipment on site.
- Logistics for pedestrian safety. Segregate administration building with fence and controlled gate from the operation facility.

- Noise/dust protection.

2.1.4 Means of Escape

General Requirements

All areas, equipment and buildings should be arranged and equipped with means of egress to ensure that it is generally possible to turn away from the source of a hazard and make a safe escape.

In general, at least two escape routes shall be provided from all areas and buildings. Single escape routes shall only be allowed for short distances leading to alternate routes, or from tall vessels/equipment where an alternate route is either not possible or would be of no benefit in escaping a hazardous situation.

Escape Routes

Escape routes are defined as unobstructed routes which lead from the workplace, or hazardous area, to a designated meeting area.

The following standards are applied when designing an escape facility:

- Escapes routes shall be located around the perimeter of the working area. They shall be level with minimal changes in direction and/or elevation.
- The configuration of the primary escape routes shall provide adequate room for fire and rescue teams to operate unhindered. Where changes in elevation of escape routes occur, ramps or stairways shall be provided.
- Every escape route and assembly point shall be readily accessible, unobstructed, and well-marked. Equipment and fixtures located along escape routes shall be recessed so as not to reduce the effective width of the passageway.
- Emergency routes and exits requiring illumination must be equipped with emergency lighting of adequate intensity to function in the event of lighting failure.
- Escape routes in process areas shall follow the most direct path from the immediate hazard to an area of reduced hazard and must avoid directing personnel escaping from a nonhazardous area through a hazardous area to reach safety.
- The primary escape routes shall preferably be on a path frequently used and large enough for the flow of people. Secondary escape routes shall be less frequently used paths, large enough for a few people.

2.1.5 Area Classification

General

If the process includes any material capable of forming explosive atmospheres (e.g. gas or very fine dust), hazardous equipment schedules and area classification (ATEX zones) drawings shall be prepared and shall include the following information:

- Identification of sources of release (e.g., seals, flanges).
- The classification and extent of all hazardous zones.
- Notes regarding selection of electrical equipment.
- Type of ventilation.
- Grade of release (continuous, primary, secondary).
- Temperature classification.

The layout and design of the facilities shall ensure that the control rooms and electrical rooms are non-hazardous by location and/or by positive pressurization via the ventilation system.

Equipment selection

Electrical equipment installed in hazardous areas shall be suitable for use in the appropriate area classification and shall comply with the requirements of IEC 60079 and be certified by a recognized international authority.

2.1.6 Process and Safety Systems

Shutdown System

Emergency shutdown system (ESD) must provide a safe and effective shutdown of plant and equipment items through the isolation of electrical equipment and the segmentation of hazardous inventories in response to process upsets, fire, or powder releases. The ESD shall be designed, as far as reasonably practicable, to:

- Automatically detect abnormal operational and equipment conditions.
- Alert the operator in the control room.
- Execute actions to mitigate the consequences of the incident or hazard, including the isolation of flammable inventories, and shutting down non-essential equipment.
- Return the process to a safe and stable condition.
- The ESD system shall be designed to 'fail safe', ensuring that in the event of a control power loss, all systems will revert to the safest condition possible.
- The objective is to ultimately prevent escalation, enable personnel to escape to a safe place and prevent further damage to the plant and equipment.

2.1.7 Electrical Safety Philosophy

Electrical power supplies pose a hazard to personnel if not managed effectively. Measures must be implemented to protect personnel from inadvertent contact with live electrical components. There is also a risk of fire or explosion resulting from overheating of cables or equipment in the event of a malfunction causing excessive localized current flow.

Design should consider the use of automatic protective systems to detect local circuit failures and isolate equipment before overheating can escalate.

The design must ensure compliance with the **Electricity at Work Regulations**. These Regulations outline principles of electrical safety applicable to all electrical systems and equipment, regardless of their manufacture or installation date.

The fundamental requirements of the Regulations may be summarised as follows:

- All systems, equipment and conductors shall be designed, constructed, installed and maintained to ensure highest practical level of safety.
- Every work activity, including operation, use and maintenance of a system, as well as work near a system, shall be carried out in a manner that does not pose a danger.
- NO live working shall take place unless absolutely essential and, in such circumstances, specific precautions shall be taken.
- Any equipment provided under the Regulations for protecting persons working on or near electrical equipment must be suitable for its intended use, be maintained in a condition suitable for that use, and be properly used.
- All personnel shall be effectively trained and supervised.
- Responsibility shall be effectively clear.
- All equipment and tools shall be appropriate for safe working practices.

2.1.8 Personnel Safety

Eyewashes and Safety Showers

Eyewashes and/or safety shower (EW/SS) facilities shall be provided wherever there is a potential risk of personnel exposure to:

- Eye or skin irritants.
- Materials handled at elevated temperatures.
- Injurious chemicals that can cause immediate or irreversible damage on contact or that have adverse systemic effects upon contact.

EW/SS facilities shall be in unobstructed areas and positioned near sources of exposure, within 15 meters of equipment handling hazardous chemicals.

Hot Surfaces

Equipment or piping with the potential to reach temperatures exceeding 60°C (140°F) that may be touched during normal operating duties must be insulated or guarded to prevent personnel injuries.

2.2 Human Factor Engineering

2.2.1 Introduction

The International Labor Organization (ILO) and the International Ergonomics Association (IEA) share the common goals of improving worker wellbeing, occupational safety and health, and the sustainability of workers and work systems. Effective human factors/ergonomics (HFE) are indispensable for supporting life and work in the 21st century. Without attention to HFE in design, work systems cannot adequately support the sustainability of workers, organizations, or societies.

This document explicitly highlights the value proposition of HFE, focusing on worker wellbeing and rights through the application of principles and guidelines for designing and managing HFE in work systems.

The document aims to assist in ensuring worker and organizational safety, health, wellbeing, and sustainability. These HFE principles and guidelines apply across all sectors and occupations, underpinning the creation of decent work, characterized by economic, psychological, and occupational security, safety, and health as well as equal opportunity and treatment for women and men.

Principles for HFE design and management of work systems presented in this document are:

Principle 1: Ensure worker safety, health, and wellbeing in the optimization of work systems as a top priority.

Principle 2: Design and manage work systems to ensure organizational and worker alignment, continuous evaluation and learning, and sustainability.

Principle 3: Create a safe, healthy, and sustainable work environment from a holistic perspective, understanding and providing for human needs.

These principles focus on respecting the individual and social integrity of workers, on creating safe and healthy workspaces.

Human Factors and Ergonomics (HFE) is a “sociotechnical” approach to systems design. It recognizes that any complex technological system that involves people is critically dependent on the organizational and social context in which it operates.

The term “ergonomics” is also used interchangeably with HFE by many organizations. However, Human Factors Engineering is broader in scope than the traditional Ergonomics. The UK HSE uses the following definition of Human Factors, from its publication *Reducing error and influencing behavior* (HSG48): 'Human Factors refer to environmental, organizational and job factors, and human and individual characteristics, which influence behavior at work in a way which can affect health and safety. A simple way to view Human Factors is to think about three aspects: the job, the individual and the organization and how they impact on people's health and safety-related behavior.'

HFE is a multidisciplinary approach to engineering that focuses on the integration of the five elements illustrated on the Human Factors Engineering ‘star’:

Figure 4: Scope and elements of Human Factor Engineering.

The five points of the star are:

1. **People:** The characteristics, capabilities, expectations, limitations, experiences and needs of the people who will operate, maintain, support, and use the facilities.
2. **Work:** The nature of the work involved in operating, maintaining, and supporting the facility.

3. **Work Organization:** How the people are organized, in terms of, for example, team structures, responsibilities, working hours and Shift schedules.
4. **Equipment:** The equipment and technology used, including the way equipment is laid out, and the elements that people need to interact with, both physically and mentally.
5. **Environment:** The work environment in which people are expected to work, including the climate, lighting, noise, vibration, and exposure to other health hazards.

A focus on the integration between these five elements is the unique – and often critical – perspective that Human Factors Engineering brings to the development of socio-technical systems.

Using a Human Factors and Ergonomics (HFE) approach to analyze, understand, and design human work in Industry can be highly beneficial.

This document describes the plan and philosophy for the eLITHE Project conversion facility Human Factors Engineering (HFE) program and human-system interface (HSI) design.

The purpose of the HFE design program is to provide an iterative, human-centered approach for the design and operation of the eLITHE Conversion Facility.

Benefits of a proper integration of HFE in the project include:

- Reduce risk to health, personal and process safety, and the environment.
- Improvements in HSE performance, and reduced operational HSE risk;
- Eliminate, reduce the likelihood of or mitigate the consequences of human error.
- Improve human efficiency and productivity, thereby enhancing operational performance.
- Reduction in CAPEX by contributing to more efficient design and avoiding the need for expensive changes and/or re-work late in the design phase.
- Minimize the need for re-work or changes during or after construction.
- Reduction in life cycle costs for operating and maintaining facilities (OPEX).
- Enhanced user commitment.

The human-centered approach to the design also ensures that during operation:

- Tasks are carried out according to defined time and performance criteria.
- Situation awareness is supported through the HSI, operating procedures, training, staffing levels and personnel qualifications.
- Vigilance is maintained over plant operations as supported by the HSI design.
- Workloads are kept at acceptable levels.
- Personnel errors are minimized, and error detection and recovery capabilities are supported.

Table 3: Acronym List – Human Factor Engineering.

Acronym	Definition
ALARP	As Low as Reasonably Practicable
BAT	Best Available Techniques
CAPX	Capital Expenditure
COMAH	Control of Major Accident Hazards
SIL	Safety Integrity Level
HSE	Health, Safety and Environment
HSI	Human System interface
HFE	Human Factor Engineering
HF	Human Factor
HRA	Human Reliability Analysis
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HAZOP	Hazards and Operability
HAZID	Hazards Identification
ESD	Emergency Shutdown System
MAH	Major Accident Hazards
OPEX	Operating Expenditure
PS	Performance Standards
PIF	Performance Influence Factor
SCE	Safety Critical Element
SCTA	Safety Critical Task Analysis
TRA	Task Requirement Analysis

2.2.2 HFE and Human Risk

Situations where human error contributes to major incidents are often a consequence of inappropriate organizational arrangements or breakdowns in operational working practices.

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Figure 5 illustrates the relationship between HFE and human error / behavior. To interpret **Figure 5**, assume some total set of potentially significant human-related risks. The left-hand axis of the figure indicates the proportion of this set that can be mitigated by design and engineering controls, system controls (i.e., safety management system, permit to work, procedures, etc.) and human controls (i.e., competent people with good attitude to safety who are fit to work and are properly supervised, etc.).

Figure 5: Role of HFE in strengthening engineered defenses against human-related risks.

Maximum Possible: Even if everything theoretically possible is done, design and engineering controls cannot control all human-related risks. The effectiveness of design and engineering controls in mitigating risk of human failure will depend on many factors and is likely to change over time as facilities age. The gap is made up through a combination of system and human controls.

ALARP: Applying the criteria of doing what is “reasonably practical” rather than what is theoretically possible (and assuming an 80/20 rule of diminishing returns) – the effectiveness of both engineering and system controls are reduced. Consequently, the reliance on human controls is increased.

Achieved: in many cases, as investigation of major incidents repeatedly shows, the risk associated with human factors is not reduced to ALARP through engineering controls. The same argument can be applied to system controls (badly written, inaccessible, or impractical procedures, lack of supervision or competence, etc.). The consequence is that human controls are again relied on to fill the increased gap.

Therefore, one way of viewing HFE is as a discipline concerned with ensuring that engineering and system controls against human unreliability are designed, implemented, and maintained in a way that reduces the reliance on human behavior and control.

2.2.3 Conceptual Model for Applying HFE in Design

Table 4 summarizes the conceptual basis of the process for applying HFE on ELITHE Conversion Facility project.

HFE technical requirements exist in several sources, including regulations, international, national and industry standards.

HFE requirements may be a combination of prescriptive, goal-oriented, and process requirements.

Table 4: HFE Requirements in Regulations, Industry Standards and Company Specifications.

HFE Requirements in Regulations, Industry Standards and Company Specifications		
Prescriptive	Goal-oriented	Process
<p><u>Examples:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workspace envelope • Ladder dimensions • Headroom clearance 	<p><u>Examples:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support human error ALARP demonstration • Support situational awareness. 	<p><u>Examples:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Valve criticality analysis • 3D model design review • Task requirements analysis

2.2.3.1 Prescriptive Requirements

Prescriptive HFE requirements specify distances, sizes, space, weight, etc. that engineers and designers can directly apply to technical drawings, use in calculations, etc. An example would be the specification for minimum clearance for headroom above walkways.

Once an appropriate technical baseline has been agreed, the HFE process during design and development is focused on ensuring compliance with these requirements. This is usually achieved via appropriate design reviews (e.g., reviews of isometric design drawings, 3D models, control room layouts, etc.).

2.2.3.2 Goal-oriented Requirements

Project-specific goal-oriented HFE requirements may be identified in regulations or standards, derived from specified project safety requirements, or identified from hazard and operability (HAZOP) studies. Goal-oriented HFE requirements specify the goal or objective that is to be achieved, but not the specific design parameters to be applied.

Examples include requirements such as 'reducing the potential for human error to ALARP' or to 'provide HMI graphics that support control room operator situational awareness'.

A range of HFE analyses and activities is typically necessary to translate identified goals into specific technical requirements that can then be implemented in design.

2.2.3.3 Process Requirements

Process requirements specify the activities that are expected to be carried out to implement HFE on a project (for example, task requirement analysis, valve criticality analysis, 3D model review).

2.2.4 Project HFE Strategy

The HFE approach for ELITHE project will be a combination of prescriptive, goal-oriented and process requirements in DFS phase as below:

- Review Standards, Local Regulations and Company Guidelines
- Workspace specifications during design.
- Consideration of HFE during HAZOP review.
- Facility/Plant Layout Design Review (3D model review)

Valve criticality analysis, safety critical task analysis, control room analysis & design review, human machine interface (HMI) analysis & review, and alarm systems analysis & review will be conducted in the next project phase, if required.

2.2.5 HFE Activities

Human Factor Engineering establishes the framework for the workspace design requirements include horizontal access, for walkways and structures, vertical access for stairs and ladders, manways, means of escape or emergency egress to be implemented in the design and reviewed in the 3D model review.

As well Human Factor Engineering will include Process Control, Operation and Safeguarding operator actions.

At DFS stage, the design is increased in detail, with systems and individual pieces of equipment shown to scale and in their proposed layout, location, and arrangement within the facility. The proposed arrangement and configuration can be adequately judged to progress to the next stages of the design process. During this phase, human factors are typically influenced as part of the following activities:

- Overall facility layout
- Unit layout
- Equipment design

- Process control design
- Building design

2.2.6 HFE Specification for Workplace Design

HFE specification for workspace specifies the minimum acceptable Human Factors Engineering requirements and gives recommendations for the design and layout of equipment and workspaces. The purpose of this specification is to ensure the arrangement created in the design allows for efficient and safe access and manual handling during operation and maintenance under all normal, upset/emergency and weather conditions by the full range of potential personnel.

HFE design specifications cover key aspects of facility design, including:

- walkways and emergency egress routes.
- elevated platforms.
- stairways and ladders.
- lighting arrangements, and
- labelling and signage.

2.2.6.1 Anthropometrics

The minimum dimensions for standing space, although based on static anthropometrics, do allow to some degree for dynamic conditions as well as accommodation of summer clothing and light PPE, but do not include allowances for cold weather PPE or respiratory protection e.g., self-contained breathing apparatus (SCBA).

All standing dimensions include a 25 mm allowance for footwear. Dimensions, where appropriate and depending on the source data, have been rounded off to the nearest 10 mm.

2.2.6.2 Minimum Volumes

Standing Volume

Standing space shall be provided for operators or maintainers in accordance with the minimum dimensions shown in **Figure 6**.

Figure 1 Minimum volume dimensions for a standing posture

Table 1 Minimum volume dimensions in a standing posture

Parameter		Minimum Dimensions
A	Width	700 mm (28 in)
B	Depth	700 mm (28 in)
C	Height	2100 mm (84 in)

Figure 6: Minimum volume dimensions in a standing posture.

Squatting/kneeling volume

Squatting/kneeling space shall be provided for operators or maintainers having to interface with equipment located at a height of 810 mm or below, in accordance with the minimum dimensions shown in **Figure 7**.

Figure 2 Minimum volume dimensions for a squatting/kneeling posture

Table 2 Minimum volume dimensions for a squatting/kneeling posture

Parameter		Minimum Dimensions
A	Width	900 mm (36 in)
B	Depth	900 mm (36 in)
C	Height	1300 mm (51 in)

Figure 7: Minimum volume dimensions for a Squatting/kneeling posture.

Supine, prone, and crawling posture

Workspaces for supine, prone and crawling postures used for inspection purposes shall be designed as per the clearance requirements specified in **Figure 8**.

Figure 3 Minimum cross-sectional area for supine, prone and crawling posture

Table 3 Minimum cross-sectional area for supine, prone and crawling posture

Parameter	Minimum Dimensions	
A	Height	900 mm (36 in)
B	Width	700 mm (28 in)

Figure 8: Minimum cross-sectional for Supine, prone and crawling posture.

2.2.6.3 Horizontal Access (Walkways and Platforms)

Walkways

Walkways on packaged units or on vessel access platforms (e.g., columns and pressure vessels) between the vessel piping or other obstruction and guardrail shall be 750 mm minimum in width. (According to PO-ENG-AES-1700-102)

Walkways other than on packaged units or vessel access platforms shall be 900 mm (36 in) minimum in width with additional width required for operating aisles or stretcher accessible routes from any location in or on a structure or building.

Operating aisles and walkways designated as a stretcher accessible route from any location in or on a structure or building shall be 1200 mm (48 in) minimum in width.

Head clearance shall be as per local regulatory requirements but in no case be less than a minimum of 2100 mm (84 in) for the full length and width of all walkways, at the primary access point of an area and around equipment and valves where operators pass during normal operations and non-turn around maintenance.

Walkways shall be kept free of all obstructions and protrusions (e.g., valve stems, piping steelwork, instrument stands).

Walking surfaces

Walking surfaces shall be as follows:

- Flush (< 4 mm (1/4 in)) change in elevation) at all joints to eliminate tripping hazards.
- Provide traction for safe passage of workers using one of the following:
 - Serrated grating (preferred).

- Standard brush finish concrete.
- Paint or finishes with grit or slip resistance enhancements.

Grating shall be used for the walking surface on stairs, ramps, platforms and decks if any of the following apply:

- When the presence of precipitation is anticipated.
- When the presence of wetting by operations or maintenance tasks is anticipated.
- In all cases where there is the potential for accumulation of liquids or loose solids that might increase the risk of slips and falls unless solid flooring is required (e.g., for containment).

Checkered plates shall only be installed with the use of slip resistant enhancing coating or finishing.

Elevated platforms

A permanent platform or standing surface shall be provided for all operational and non-turn-around maintenance tasks not within reach or view but requiring the use of both hands and unobstructed view. It is unsafe to require or encourage personnel to stand on surfaces that were not specifically designed as standing surfaces. This will provide operators/maintainers with a stable standing surface that does not require them to stand on stair treads or ladder rungs while performing work.

Structural steel members in the base frame are considered inappropriate as standing surfaces. A permanent platform shall be provided for maintenance access to manways or other service openings and for temporary storage or lay down of blinds, vessel entry or for handling and storage of consumable materials such as catalyst or desiccants when 4.0 m or more above grade.

Elevated interconnectivity between adjacent structures, vessels and furnaces should be provided in their design as requested by Principal (Operations discipline).

- Adjacent furnaces in the same group should provide platform interconnectivity at each operating level.

Platforms shall not be less than 760 mm wide or the swing radius of a self-closing safety gate plus 460 mm and 900 mm deep with the following exceptions:

- Platforms which are used exclusively for standing (e.g., just to reach a valve) shall be no less than 610 mm wide and 760 mm deep.
- Landing platforms used to access a vertical ladder shall be no less than the following:
 - 650 mm (24 in) wide (See dimension A in **Figure 9**).

- 750 mm (30 in) deep or equal to the depth of the cage (See dimension B in **Figure 9**).

Figure 9: Landing platforms used to access a vertical ladder.

Walkways on elevated platforms for vessels/columns/towers/spheres shall provide a minimum of 700 mm clear access between any object (including insulation and cladding) and the guardrail; see dimensions D and E in **Figure 10** (According to PO-ENG-AES-1700-102).

The standing surface of the platform shall not be more than 1.2 m below the centre of manways.

Figure 10: Vessel elevated platform access clearances.

2.2.6.4 Vertical Access (Stairs, Ladders and Ramps)

Except for stand-alone vessels or columns/towers not located in supporting structures, stairs shall be provided for access to and egress from the following:

- elevated platforms, walkways, and other elevated work areas where the frequency of use is once per shift or more.
- battery limit platforms.

Stair widths shall comply with **Table 5**.

Table 5: Stair widths table.

Location	Minimum width (inside handrails)
Stairs other than those designated as stretcher accessible route, from a location in or on a building or structure (Onshore or Offshore).	900 mm (36 in) ¹
Stairs designated as stretcher accessible route, from a location in or on a structure or buildings (Onshore or Offshore).	1200 mm (48 in)

¹This width is the minimum width for an exit or escape route where fewer than 50 people are expected to be present.

Head clearance above each tread of the stair shall be 2300 mm (according to ASD-1700-102-122)

The angle of stair inclination recommended is 30° to 38°. (According to POENG- AES-1700-102).

Riser height and tread depth (tread run or going) for the approved stair inclinations (angles) shall be as per the minimum dimensions provided in **Table 6**.

Table 6: Minimum dimensions for rise/tread combinations table.

Angle to horizontal	Riser Height		Tread Depth (run/going) ¹	
	mm	inches	mm	inches
30	165	6.5	279	11
32	171	6.75	273	10.75

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33	178	7	267	10.5
35	184	7.25	260	10.25
36	191	7.5	254	10
38	197	7.75	248	9.75
40	203	8	241	9.5
45 ²	222	9.5	222	9.5

¹This is the effective tread depth i.e., not including any overlap as per ISO 14122-3.

²Applicable for flare boom stairs.

Rise height and tread depth shall be uniform throughout any flight of stairs, including any foundation structure used as one or more treads of the stairs.

This means that riser heights and tread depths are not allowed to change within a stair run.

Riser heights and tread depths should be uniform in design throughout the structure or facility.

Stair landings shall be as wide as the stair to which they are attached and have a depth equal to the width of the stair as a minimum.

The top tread of a stair shall be flush with the walking surface to which the stair is attached.

Coaming/containment shall not present a tripping hazard by providing clear landing areas as follows:

- at the top or bottom landings of stairs a clear area shall be provided equivalent to a stair landing.
- at the top or bottom of fixed vertical ladders a clear area shall be provided equivalent to a landing platform.

The surface of treads on exterior stairs shall be constructed of open steel grating or fiberglass grating.

Flat plate or checkered plate shall be treated with slip-resistant material in locations where snow, other precipitation or accumulation of solid materials are possible, that will reduce the slip resistance of the surface.

Individual steps, comprised of tread surfaces only, should be attached directly to a structure (e.g., bulkhead) to change vertical elevations where space is not available for stair or vertical ladder and the change in elevation is less than 500 mm.

The maximum riser height for a single individual step should be 300 mm.

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Winding stairs shall only be installed on tanks, spheres, or round structures, excluding the wave zone of hull columns, whose diameter is greater than 1500 mm (60 in), and where a normal i.e., straight run stair design is structurally inappropriate.

Winding stairs should ascend in a clockwise direction to allow the stair handrail to be on the right-hand side during descent when a single handrail is provided.

Vertical fixed ladders

The maximum height of a single run ladder complying with all fall protection requirements shall preferably be 6 m, but not more than 9.0m” (According to PO-ENG-AES-1700-102).

Where there are several runs, the height of a single ladder run between the departure area and the nearest platform or between consecutive rest platforms shall be no more than 6 m.

First ladder rung centreline shall be 300 mm maximum / 100 mm minimum from top of grade or walking surface.

At landings, the step across distance from the centreline of the rung for step through ladders and walking/standing surface edge shall not be less than 180 mm or more than 300 mm.

At landings, the step across distance from the centreline of the rung for sidestep ladders and walking/standing surface edge shall not be less than 380 mm or more than 510 mm.

Ladders which protrude through a platform shall be designed to satisfy the following:

- the ladder opening is protected by a cage with a swing gate, open in the direction of the next ladder.
- the platform is extended with a walkway around the back of the cage.
- the minimum clear width on the walkway around the back of the cage is 700 mm.

Ladders shall be located so the maximum distance from the edge of the ladder to any object that has to be reached for operations or physical inspection purposes, does not exceed 460 mm.

Ladders should be oriented such that the climber faces the structure or vessel while climbing.

The use of step-through ladders shall be subject to the approval of the principal. Sidestep orientation at the top of vertical ladders is preferred due to the increased climber safety that it provides when transitioning from or onto the ladder at height.

Ladder shall not interfere with the movement or removal of any item or cover, including the swing of manways.

The use of inclined ladders shall be subject to the approval of the principal.

Ladders on elevated platforms, located 1500 mm or less from the guard railing, as measured from the ladder centreline to either side and on the climbing side, or 1220 mm or less for sites subject to US regulation, shall meet one of the following:

- extend the railing to a height of no less than 700 mm below the cage, for no less than 1500 mm on either side of the ladder centerline on all sides not meeting the distance criteria.
- extend the straps from the cage to the guard railing on all sides not meeting the distance criteria.

Ramps and sloped walkways

Ramps should be used for changing from one walking or working surface to another when any of the following conditions exist:

- When the change in vertical elevation is less than 610 mm.
- When it is necessary to move people, and vehicles, or materials via a single technique rather than through individual vehicle/material ramps and separate personnel stairs.
- When a ramp would allow more efficient personnel egress along an emergency access/egress route, if the angle of inclination is 7 degrees or less.
- When a person is hand-carrying bulky loads or loads more than 13.6 kg.

Depending on the ramps/sloped walkway intended usage, the inclines in **Table 7** shall apply.

Table 7: Minimum dimensions for rise/tread combinations table.

RAMP USE	INCLINE IN DEGREES
Pedestrian Traffic without Materials Handling	8° (Preferred) – 15° (Maximum)
Pedestrian Traffic with Materials Handling	4° (Preferred) – 7° (Maximum)

Ramps used for movement of all manual or self-propelled material-handling carriers or vehicular movement shall provide a minimum clear width of 610 mm on each side of the carrier or vehicle.

Pedestrian ramps more than 4 degrees angle of inclination shall have slip-resistant surfaces.

Ramps more than 10 degrees of inclination shall have cross cleats as follows:

- maximum spacing 410 mm (16 in).
- extending the full width of the ramp.
- at right angles to the direction of travel.

2.2.7 Overall eLITHE Conversation Facility and Unit Plot Plans Development

Overall facility and unit plot plans shall be designed and laid out to suite the operator and equipment / devices interaction. The following factors that can affect human performance will be taken into considerations during ELITHE Conversion overall facility and units plot plan development:

- Layout
- Manways
- Platform Access
- Physical Activity
- Accessibility
- Equipment Accessibility & Clearance

2.2.7.1 Layout

The design of the arrangement and size of physical workspaces shall accommodate the following:

1. the number of personnel required to perform the task.
2. the ambient work environment (temperature, noise, vibration, lighting, powder exposure).
3. the actions (physical movements and application of force) to be undertaken, including use of multiple pieces of equipment or instrumentation and equipment.
4. the postures that operators will be required to assume.
5. confinement of the manipulation or use of equipment, required tools and internals to inside the guardrail.

Items or components requiring visual monitoring/inspection for operation, shall be visible from an approachable and safe operator position, i.e., on an adjacent walkway, access platform or internal walkway on skid, or in space around equipment that is intended for human access.

Items or components requiring physical access for operation, shall be accessible from an approachable and safe operator position, i.e., on an adjacent walkway, access platform or internal walkway on skid, or in space around equipment that is intended for human access.

Items or components that require routine inspection, planned maintenance or repair shall not require disconnection of piping and cabling or removal of additional or non-failed equipment other than piping spools.

Space for the tools and largest removable component shall be provided around equipment (e.g., compressors, pumps, motors, heat exchanger bundles, valves, filters) for lay down during maintenance activities.

Laydown space provided for maintenance shall be kept clear of all piping, cable trays, panels, instrument stands and any other obstructions.

Equipment or components requiring mechanical assistance for removal should be located so that they will not prevent access to other more frequently accessed items.

Fragile items that could be damaged in the process of gaining access to other equipment or maintenance activities shall be protected.

Check points, adjustment points, test points, and labels shall be accessible and visible during maintenance.

Space shall be provided for the use of test equipment and other required tools without difficulty or hazard.

Equipment layout should be prioritized for accessibility in the following order:

- safety critical equipment.
- process critical items from hazard and operability studies, i.e., items most critical to system operation.
- items which reduce the safety or efficiency of the process when removed due maintenance therefore requiring rapid maintenance.
- all other items.

Pull or removal spaces provided for maintenance or repair of valves and other equipment shall be kept clear of all piping, cable trays, panels, instrument stands and any other obstructions.

The pull or removal space shall provide room for the personnel performing the tasks, tools required, assisted lifting or support equipment, and transport devices (if used) to move the item from the area.

Railings restricting pull spaces shall be removable.

2.2.7.2 Manways

The design of manways and other access/egress openings shall incorporate the following in their design and positioning:

- Allowances for protective equipment (i.e., PPE, RPE, weather resistant clothing) that the operator will be required to wear under normal and emergency operating conditions.
- Task considerations including the carriage of tools, equipment, and materials.
- Anthropometrics of the personnel population.
- Emergency rescue requirements.
- Direction of entry, whether horizontal or vertical.

Clearances around manways on vessel access platforms shall be per Figure 11 and Table 4. Circular manways or vessel skirt openings, requiring full body access, shall have a minimum inside or clear diameter of DN 600. If top entry is required on vertical or horizontal vessels, then minimum size of the manway shall be DN 750 to accommodate ladders. Vessel/column tray access openings (requiring full body access) shall have a minimum diameter of 610 mm (24 in) if circular or as per Table 4. Dimensions for an opening requiring full body access other than manways, shall be per Figure 11 and Table 4.

Figure 11: Dimension for rectangular openings in horizontal and vertical orientations

Table 8: Minimum dimension for rectangular and square openings in horizontal and vertical location/orientation.

Hatch Location/Orientation	Rectangle		Square
Horizontal Surface (Top or Bottom access)	A (Depth)	360 mm (14 in)	580 mm (23 in)
	B (Width)	560 mm (22 in)	
Vertical Surface (Side access)	C (Height)	810 mm (32 in)	660 mm (26 in)
	D (Width)	460 mm (18 in)	

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	E (Height)	410 mm (16 in)	
	F (Width)	610 mm (24 in)	

2.2.7.3 Platform Access

Access to platforms should occur by permanently installed stairs or ladders.

Stairs, not ladders, shall be provided where:

- Personnel are required to carry large tools or pieces of equipment up or down the structure.
- Equipment must be accessed, or personnel evacuated during emergencies; and
- Equipment is frequently accessed (i.e. once per shift on average).

2.2.7.4 Physical Activity

The following points are to be considered:

- Material handling and lifting heavy components by fixed or mobile hoisting equipment.
- Space reservation for maintenance as part of layout
- Drop down area.
- Waste transferring.

2.2.7.5 Accessibility

General

The following are the minimum requirements for accessibility to principal operating components.

From Grade or Platform

- Control valves and bypass valves.
- Safety valves (except thermal relief valves).
- Battery limit valves.

From Permanent Ladder

- Level instruments on towers and vessels.
- Pressure indicators.
- Temperature indicators.
- Handholes.
- Sample take-off points.

From Portable Device or Scaffolding

- Check valves.
- Pressure connections (except indicators).
- Temperature connections (except indicators).
- Manholes on vessels with an elevation of 4000 mm and below

2.2.7.6 Equipment Accessibility & Clearance

Access to inside and outside of equipment for regular operation, intervention, reading, maintenance, inspection, or monitoring should occur from grade, a platform, stairs, or a permanent ladder. Correct access also includes clearance around equipment, the height of installation, and the position relative to equipment.

The location of safety equipment i.e., manual alarm call points, safety shower, eye wash, fire-fighting equipment, etc. shall be determined based on how employees use the equipment in responding to emergencies.

Vertical Clearance:

- 6.0 m over main roads and crane access.
- 4.0 m for truck access and plant roads.
- 2.7 m for normal overhead in the units and forklift truck access.
- 2.1 m for normal headroom over walkways and platforms.

Horizontal Clearance:

- 0.75 m for access ways and walkways.
- 1.0 m for escape passages and maintenance areas.
- 2.8 m for forklift truck access.

2.2.8 Process Control, Operation and Safeguarding Philosophy

The design of the process control and safeguarding systems determines the required actions by operations personnel and therefore the likelihood of human error. Also, the system can prevent human error.

Control System and Safeguarding System, as the Emergency Shutdown System (ESD), should take following into account.

Automated Versus Manual Actions – Manual actions take more decision time. Automated actions have a higher likelihood of unnecessary deployment (false positive), whereas manual actions have a higher likelihood of non-deployment when necessary (false negative). The choice for either of the concepts is dependent on the operations philosophy.

Interlocks – The use of interlocks can prevent human error. If the process control system disallows the execution of an activity, human error can be reduced.

Early detection and isolation of hazardous releases substantially limit the consequences resulting from an emergency. ESD functionality shall be provided for situations where rapid isolation is necessary.

2.2.8.1 ESD Functionality

The ESD functionality shall provide means for minimizing the risk to the facility caused by abnormal operating conditions and external hazards as a part of the fire fighting and protection philosophy for the plant.

To achieve this, the ESD function shall provide means of shutting down and isolating the process systems and equipment so that any abnormal condition is prevented, mitigated, or otherwise controlled.

2.2.8.2 ESD Initiation

An ESD shall be manually initiated upon detection of abnormal operating conditions. This initiation shall be accomplished via dedicated hard-wired switches located in the CR.

Initiation of an ESD switch shall establish a state at the ESD system outputs such that the plant attains a safe state. To realize this, the system shall utilize fail safe techniques, which include the following features:

- System operates in an energized state for normal operation.
- The safe state of the plant will be established by de-energizing solenoid valves or relay.

Additionally, where an operator cannot respond to a perceived emergency in sufficient time to mitigate an incident, automatic executive action may be required. High integrity sensors shall automatically initiate an ESD. Generally, these functions shall be limited to specific equipment protection. In these cases, the level of redundancy and integrity shall be determined by a SIL classification of the hazard.

2.2.8.3 ESD Operation

The ESD system covers protection of the plant ranging from specific sections to the entire complex. The ESD system will be operated on the following basis:

- The operator's decision to shut down a particular ESD level will be based on various signals received in the control room onto the safety console, such as gas alarms, fire

alarms and radioed messages from the outsider operator, backed up by the ability of the operator to view the area by closed circuit television.

- After activation of an ESD, the operator will wait until the emergency has been resolved before resetting the ESD valves. The reset would be on a group, or in specific cases, on an individual basis. Resetting the ESD will open the circuits except were local inspections.
- are required.
- Any electrical equipment will not automatically restart following a reset of the ESD. Instead, the reset of ESD will allow the operator to restart the equipment in an orderly sequence.

2.3 Permit to Work Procedure

2.3.1 Introduction

A permit to work can be considered as a specialised Safe System of Work under which certain high risk activities may only be carried out with specific permission from the Authorised Person.

Permits to Work (PTW) are an important means of ensuring the Health and Safety of employees, contractors and other people, therefore fulfilling the Trust duty of care. Non-routine high risk tasks such as Hot Work, work on live electrical systems, maintenance in confined spaces, etc. can produce health and safety risks over and above those normally encountered. Therefore, a PTW is a specialised risk assessment to control these risks

A permit-to-work system aims to ensure that proper consideration is given to the risks of a particular job or simultaneous activities at site. Whether manually or electronically generated, the permit is a detailed document which authorises certain people to carry out specific work at a specific site and time, and which sets out the main precautions needed to complete the job safely.

The objective of this Procedure is to define requirements for site implementation of a Permit to Work system that controls the risks to people, the environment, installations and the Company's reputation in an effective way.

This is achieved by establishing clear agreements between the authorised person representing the Owner, the Contractor carrying out the work (Permit Applicant) and the person accepting the Permit to Work on behalf of the Contractor (Permit Acceptor).

The procedure will ensure that all personnel have an understanding of the Permit To Work system and those with specific roles have received adequate training and instruction to ensure that they are capable of undertaking those duties.

Different types of jobs require a specific PTW before being carried out. When these permits are not issued and implemented effectively, personnel are exposed to potential hazards. A poorly implemented PTW system remains one of the major causes of some industrial accidents. Those responsible for the preparation of a PTW system should have adequate training, understand the scope of the job for which the permit is prepared and communicate every detail of the permit to those that will use it in line with the regulations and procedures.

The ceramic industry, like other industries using a PTW system, can improve its implementation by making it more reliable, descriptive, and simple to understand, while ensuring proper supervision and monitoring throughout its issuance, use and post-use phases.

The objectives and functions of such a system can be summarised as:

- Ensuring the proper authorisation of designated work. This may include certain types of work or any type of work within certain designated areas, excluding normal operations;
- Clearly communicating to workers the exact identity, nature and extent of the job, the hazards involved, and any limitations regarding the extent of the work and the timeframe for its execution;
- Specifying the precautions to be taken, including safe isolation from potential risks such as hazardous substances, electricity and other energy forms (for details of isolation procedures and when they are appropriate see HSE guidance on The safe isolation of plant and equipment);
- Ensuring that the person in direct charge of a unit, plant or installation is aware of all hazardous work being done there;
- Providing not only a system of continuous control, but also a record showing that the nature of the work and the precautions needed have been checked by an appropriate person or people;
- Ensuring that permits are suitably displayed;
- Providing a procedure for times when work has to be suspended, ie stopped for a period before it is complete;
- Managing work activities that may interact or impact one another;
- Providing a formal handover procedure for use when a permit is issued for a period longer than one shift;
- Providing a formal hand-back procedure to ensure that the part of the plant affected by the work is in a safe condition and ready for reinstatement.

The conditions for achieving this objective are:

- The Permit Applicant, Permit Validator and Permit Acceptor agree the scope of work, which cannot be changed once the Permit to Work is issued.

- The precautions to be taken have been clearly defined and are in place prior to the start of work.
- The Permit Validator is aware of all activities and gives authorization to start work.

This procedure will apply to all Construction, Completion and Commissioning activities which remain under the control of Project Owner.

The Template List is in Annex 5.2..

Table 9: Acronym List – Permit to Work Procedure.

Acronym	Definition
HSE	Health, Safety & Environment
R&R	Roles & Responsibilities
T	Template
AT	Attached Template
RAMS	Risk Assessment & Method Statement
CSE	Confined Space Entry

2.3.2 Definitions

Permit to Work

The purpose of any Permit to Work System is to ensure that work can be carried out in a safe and controlled manner. The system provides the most efficient means of coordinating multiple work activities by competent, authorized persons.

Permit Coordinator

The appointed persons from the Owner who are authorized to issue all validated construction Permits to Work for the project, on behalf of the Site Manager. The Permit Coordinator's can issue Construction and commissioning Permits. These will include permits for Civils and Mechanical activities and work on Electrical Systems prior to energization (i.e. installation of cables, glanding and terminations etc.).

SAP

The Senior Authorized Person (SAP) who is responsible for controlling Permits to Work in accordance with the Safety Rules for Works on Mechanical Plant involving electrical isolations and the Electrical Safety Rules. He will also be responsible for controlling the Request for Energization procedure and the Mechanical / Electrical Isolation Register. The SAP will check and sign off all isolation points made by other authorized Permit Validators.

All permits for electrical Completions and Commissioning activities will be issued by the Owner SAP.

Permit Issuer

In addition to the Permit Co-Ordinator, selected members of the HSE Team have been trained and authorized to issue Validated Permits to Work for the project, on behalf of the Permit Co-Ordinator, but not on behalf of the Permit Engineer.

Permit Applicant

An individual or company who liaises with the Permit Coordinator to ensure that Risk Assessment / Method Statements, Permit Request Forms, drawings, and any other supporting documentation required is submitted to the Permit Office in a timely manner.

Permit Acceptor

A competent person who has been trained and authorized by the Permit Coordinator / Engineer to accept Permits on their own behalf or on behalf of others whose work they are controlling.

This will be a contractor supervisor for construction or commissioning personnel.

Permit Validator

A competent person who has been formally authorized by the Site manager to ensure that equipment is isolated, and precautions are sufficient to allow the work to proceed safely.

The Permit Validator will be an Authorized Discipline Supervisor (or nominated delegate) or an authorized member of the HSE Team.

At the Daily Permit Coordination Meeting all new permit applications will be reviewed.

The appropriate Construction Manager will initial each approved permit indicating their agreement to the work taking place subject to the signature of the Permit Validator and Permit Coordinator

A register of Authorized Permit Validators will be maintained.

2.3.3 Permit Identification

Should have five types of Permit in use on the project. These are:

- General Work Permit
- Hot Work Permit
- Confined Space Work Permit
- Permit to Carry Out Electrical Functional Testing
- Electrical Permit to Work

The Permit Form will be in triplicate. The top copy of the permit will be retained in the Permit Office with the other copies located at the work site

2.3.3.1 General Permit Requirements (All permit types)

All permits shall be supported by a detailed Risk Assessment and Method Statement which have been accepted as suitable by the Owner. (For commissioning activities, the Risk Assessment and Method Statement will be approved by Contractor Commissioning Supervision and suitably endorsed:

- A plot plan with the work location highlighted.
- A P&ID for mechanical work with relevant system and isolations shown.
- A Single Line Diagram for electrical work showing isolations.
- A Material Safety Data Sheet for any chemicals/products to be used.

2.3.3.2 General Work Permit

A General Work Permit will cover 'cold work' activities where specific precautions can be set.

The maximum duration for General Work Permits is 7 days, or 14 shifts, whichever is applicable.

2.3.3.3 Hot Work Permit

A Hot Work Permit is issued to prevent fires (or explosions) in circumstances where work poses a risk due to the presence of combustible / flammable materials or liquids and / or explosions, or due to the presence of a flammable atmosphere.

Work involving welding, burning, or grinding along with any other operation which creates sufficient heat to cause ignition, is classed as 'Hot Work'.

The maximum duration for Hot Work Permits is 7 days, or 14 shifts, whichever is applicable.

2.3.3.4 Confined Space Work Permit

A "confined space" means any place, including any chambers, tank, vat, silo, pit, trench, pipe, sewer, flue, well or other similar space in which, by virtue of its enclosed nature, there arises a reasonably foreseeable specified risk.

For identification and management of confined spaces. Prior to the Confined Space Work Permit being issued, an initial atmosphere test must be carried out by the Contractor and witnessed by the Owner.

If work in the confined space stops for more than one hour, a new atmosphere test must be performed, with the results recorded on the supplementary atmosphere test sheet attached to the permit.

The maximum duration for Confined Space Work Permits is 7 days, or 7 shifts, whichever is applicable.

2.3.3.5 Permit to Carry Out Electrical Functional Testing

An approved Permit to Carry out Electrical Functional Testing can be issued by the Permit Engineer (Senior Authorised Person or their nominated deputy) and accepted by the person in charge of or performing the work. The purpose of this permit is to make known the equipment on which permission is given to carry out Functional Testing, the nature of the testing and the Safe System of Work to be employed. To obtain such a permit, the Permit Applicant must make a request to the Permit Engineer. For first-time system energization, a 'Request for Energisation' form must be submitted.

2.3.3.6 Electrical Permit to Work

An approved Electrical Permit to Work can be issued by the Senior Authorised Person (or his nominated deputy) and accepted by the person in charge of, or performing the work to specify the equipment deemed safe to work on and the work to be carried out on it.

2.3.4 Procedure

2.3.4.1 Formally Authorized Persons

All Construction, pre-Commissioning and Commissioning activities will be carried out under the Owner Permit to Work procedure and all validated permits will be issued by the PTW Coordinator and the Senior Authorized Person, or their nominated deputies.

All Permit Acceptors must be assessed and formally authorized by the PTW Coordinator/Controller

2.3.4.2 Permit Requests

For all new tasks which require a Permit to Work, a Permit Request must be submitted to the Permit Office at least two working days prior to the task being started. This ensures that the Permit Coordinators/Permit Validators have sufficient time to ensure that any relevant Risk Assessment / Method Statements have been submitted and reviewed; any drawings have been submitted, along with any other relevant documentation required for the necessary permit. The Owner coordinator will review all Permit Requests during or before the Daily Permit Coordination Meeting to avoid conflicts with existing systems. The completed Permit Request must include the following information:

- Contractor name
- Location of work
- Detailed description of work
- Start date / time.
- Related documents (Risk Assessment / Method Statements etc.)
- A Plot Plan with the work location suitably highlighted.
- For Mechanical Work a P&ID showing the relevant system and associated isolations
- For Electrical Work a Single Line Drawing showing the relevant circuit and isolations
- Tools and equipment to be used.
- Any hazards which are to be expected during works and mitigations.

2.3.4.3 Permit Issue and Acceptance

The Permit Validator will sign the Permit to Work to confirm that:

- The work area has been inspected.
- The Contractor can carry out the work safely providing all precautions laid down in the Permit to Work have been taken.
- The supervision levels have been established.
- The Permit Acceptor has understood the conditions of the Permit to Work
- The work is coordinated in relation to possible interference with other work nearby
- Previous permits for the work activity have been signed off (cancelled) prior to a new permit being issued.
- The work will be monitored by the Owner Site Team to ensure compliance listed on the Permit to Work
- The work can start.

The Permit Coordinator will sign the permit to confirm that the permit meets the requirements of the Permit to Work Procedure and that the permit can be issued.

The Permit Acceptor will sign the Permit to Work to confirm that:

- The work has been discussed and agreed between the Contractor and the Owner
- The agreed precautions have been taken prior to work starting.
- A copy of the Permit to Work is kept local to the workplace.
- All persons working under the Permit to Work will be briefed on the precautions of the Permit to Work, along with the Risk Assessment / Method Statement
- A Daily Pre-Check meeting (DPC) must be conducted prior to work commencement.
- All permits will be returned to the Permit Office at the end of the day/shift for re-validation or for cancellation if the work is complete.

The area will be left in a safe and clean condition, both at the end of the working day / shift, as well as on completion of the specific task.

2.3.4.4 Cross Referencing

Other permits related to the task may be cross referenced in the relevant box on the Permit to Work, as necessary.

2.3.4.5 Suspended Permits

Permits may be suspended when:

- The scope of work changes from the original scope. If this is the case, the Contractor must submit a Risk Assessment / Method Statement Amendment Form for reassessment and inclusion of new changes / control measures.
- The agreed precautions listed in the Permit to Work or Risk Assessment / Method Statement are not being followed. (Any person seeing violation of permit conditions may stop the work)
- When the expiry date and time is over.
- The emergency alarm sounds. Restart of work should only commence with permission of the Owner who will re-sign the permit to confirm work can re start.

The Permit Coordinator withdraws the Permit to Work for any other reason.

2.3.4.6 Handover of Permits to Work

If the Permit Coordinators must leave site for any reason, they may formally handover to a nominated Permit Issuer or Discipline Supervisor, to co-ordinate and monitor Permits to Work on their behalf. In this instance, a Permit to Work Handover Form shall be completed.

If a Permit Acceptor must leave site for any reason or is unable to fully monitor those working under the Permit to Work, a handover must take place in where a new Permit Acceptor must return all permits to the Permit Office, where they will be reissued to the new Permit Acceptor.

2.3.4.7 Lost Damaged Permits

If a Permit to Work has been lost by the Contractor during work, the Permit Acceptor must inform the Permit Coordinator as soon as possible. If a search has not recovered the permit, a new Permit Request must be submitted.

If a Permit to Work has been damaged, contact must also be made with the Permit Coordinator to cancel that particular permit and issue a replacement.

2.3.4.8 Permit Amendments

Under no circumstances must a Permit to Work be changed, altered or defaced in any way. The Permit Validator is the only person authorized to change or modify any Permit to Work.

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the European Union.

Any mistakes or errors within the permit shall be crossed out with a single line and signed for by the Permit Coordinator.

Overwriting or using correction fluid invalidates any Permit to Work resulting in immediate cancellation.

Any amendments to a Permit to Work shall be carried out only with all three copies of the permit together in the presence of the Permit Acceptor, who shall then relay these amendments to the work party.

2.3.4.9 *Permit Office Diary*

Any issues found shall be recorded by the Permit Coordinators in the Permit to Work Diary. By doing this, it ensures:

- All work is thoroughly coordinated.
- Any issues which need resolving are recorded to be actioned.
- Key dates and times are recorded (i.e. Permit to Work training)

Where the work will take place outside of normal working hours, an efficient handover will take place.

2.3.4.10 *Positive Mechanical/Electrical Isolations of Section of Plant*

All isolations shall be carried out by competent, authorised persons in accordance with the requirements of the Project Isolation Procedure (LOTO).

2.3.4.11 *Cancellation and Archiving*

On completion of the task, the Permit Acceptor will clear all tools and materials, and leave the area in a safe and clean condition. Following this, the Permit must be returned to the Permit Office for cancellation by both the Permit Acceptor /Permit Validator Signatory where appropriate.

All permits which have been cancelled must be retained by the Permit Office for the duration of the project.

2.3.4.12 *Auditing the Permit to Work System*

Day to day operation of the Permit to Work System is the responsibility of the Permit Coordinator / Engineer, the Permit Acceptors, and all Permit Users (work party working under the permit).

To ensure that the Permit to Work System is being operated in line with this procedure, there is a requirement to undertake periodic audits.

2.3.4.13 *Coordination and Communications*

There will be a daily co-ordination meeting daily. Attendees will include but are not be limited to Works Contractor PTW Coordinators, Contractor Site managers, PTW Coordinator, Owner PTW staff as decided by the Owner PTW Coordinator.

2.3.4.14 *Training and Competence*

Two types of training are essential to ensure the correct use of the WPS:

- Training on the risk assessments methodology.
- Training on the Procedure that rules the WPS and its associated procedures.

The training should be provided to Execution Entities, Permit Issuers and Permit Authorizers (as a minimum) and a register should be maintained with the list of approved persons to perform these 3 roles.

The register of approved persons will be done.

A refreshment of the training should be provided at least on a yearly base and the lists revised accordingly. A revision of the lists should also be done when trainings are performed to approve more persons.

2.4 LOTO Procedure

2.4.1 Introduction

Energy sources including electrical, mechanical, hydraulic, pneumatic, chemical, thermal, or other sources in machines and equipment can be hazardous to workers. During the servicing and maintenance of machines and equipment, the unexpected startup or release of stored energy can result in injuries or fatalities.

Worker's servicing or maintaining machines or equipment may be seriously injured or killed if hazardous energy is not properly controlled. Injuries resulting from the failure to control hazardous energy during maintenance activities can be serious or fatal! Injuries may include electrocution, burns, crushing, cutting, lacerating, amputating, or fracturing body parts, and others.

Proper lockout/tagout (LOTO) practices and procedures safeguard workers from hazardous energy releases.

The primary difference between lockout and tagout lies in the devices used. The lockout device stops employees from operating the equipment while the tagout device informs them

that the equipment should not be operated. Essentially, a tagout device is the second layer of protection against unsafe equipment operation while a lockout device is the first layer.

OSHA's Lockout/Tagout requirements, describes the practices and procedures necessary to disable machinery or equipment to prevent hazardous energy release. The OSHA standard for The Control of Hazardous Energy (Lockout/Tagout) for general industry outlines measures for controlling different types of hazardous energy. The LOTO standard establishes the employer's responsibility to protect workers from hazardous energy. Employers are also required to train each worker to ensure that they know, understand, and can follow the applicable provisions of the hazardous energy control procedures:

- Proper lockout/tagout (LOTO) practices and procedures safeguard workers from the release of hazardous energy. The OSHA standard for The Control of Hazardous Energy (Lockout/Tagout) for general industry, outlines specific action and procedures for addressing and controlling hazardous energy during servicing and maintenance of machines and equipment. Employers are also required to train each worker to ensure that they know, understand, and are able to follow the applicable provisions of the hazardous energy control procedures. Workers must be trained in the purpose and function of the energy control program and have the knowledge and skills required for the safe application, usage and removal of the energy control devices.
- All employees who work in an area where energy control procedure(s) are utilized need to be instructed in their purpose and use, with a particular emphasis on the prohibition of restarting or reenergizing machines or other equipment that are locked or tagged out.
- All employees who are authorized to lockout machines or equipment and perform service and maintenance operations need to be trained to recognize hazardous energy sources in the workplace, understand the type and magnitude of energy found in the workplace, and apply appropriate methods for isolating and/or controlling the energy.
- Specific procedures and limitations relating to tagout systems where they are allowed.
- Retraining of all employees to maintain proficiency or introduce new or changed control methods.

Though the machine guarding covers exposure to hazardous energy during normal production operations, it is important to note that the OSHA lockout tagout standard applies during normal production operations if:

- the employee is required to bypass or remove machine guarding, or
- the employee could be injured due to the sudden energization of equipment.

Safety Management must be aware of common OSHA lockout/Tagout violations, such as:

- Failure to identify and isolate all energy sources.
- Failure to shut down.
- Failure to de-energize.
- Failure to drain the residual energy.
- Failure to provide lock out tag out training.
- Failure to create equipment specific LOTO procedures.
- Failure to conduct periodic LOTO inspections.
- Failure to establish a lockout tagout program.
- Failure to develop and enforce a lock out tag out policy.

Also known as LOTO steps, follow this comprehensive guide on how to properly shut down equipment:

Figure 12: Steps of Lockout Tagout Procedure.

Step 1: Preparation – During this stage, the authorized employee should investigate to identify the equipment, machine, or process to be shut down. As a safety measure, this step should also recognize which energy resources must be controlled and highlight all the potential hazards that come with it.

Step 2: Notification – In the second stage, all affected personnel should be notified of the shutdown. Essential items to communicate can include information such as the equipment to be locked out, the reason behind it, the estimated time frame of the shutdown, the authorized personnel for the shutdown, as well as who to contact for clarifications and questions.

Step 3: Shutdown – After the planning stage, the actual equipment shutdown begins. For this process, follow the shutdown procedures established by the manufacturer or the workplace itself. Turn off the controls and make sure that all the running parts of the equipment come to a total stop.

Step 4: Isolation – This stage, also called de-energization—is the part where the authorized person will be needing to remove the equipment from any energy sources it is connected to. Some equipment may need to be shut down by turning off power from the breaker or by simply shutting a valve.

Step 5: Dissipation – In simpler terms, this is the process of removing possible residual energy still in the equipment. Depending on the type of equipment or power source, residual energy can either be disconnected, restrained, relieved, or made non-hazardous.

Step 6: Lockout/Tagout – During this actual lockout/tagout stage, the equipment is locked using energy-isolating devices. The tag to be attached, meanwhile, should contain the name of the person who performed the lockout and other additional information needed.

Step 7: Isolation verification – In this last stage, all the steps conducted must be re-checked to ensure that everything is as it should be. Treat this as an opportunity to test the equipment by activating the process controls and observing the result. Non-activation of the equipment is a confirmation that energy isolation is completed.

2.4.1.1 Objective

The objective of this guide is to develop a Project specific procedure to prevent the unexpected energization, start-up or release of stored energy that may result in bodily injury or property damage during construction, testing, maintenance and servicing of machinery or equipment by ISOLATION (Lockout/Tag out (LOTO)) of that part of the installations that is related to a specified hazardous job activity.

2.4.1.2 Applicability and Compliance

The derived specific procedure shall apply to all employees and contractors within the administrative control of the Owner who work on equipment where unexpected energization, start-up, or energy release could cause injury. This includes all related construction and pre-commissioning activities and associated test equipment, test rigs, and temporary power installations within control and supervision of the Owner.

Table 10: Acronym List – LOTO Procedure.

Acronym	Definition
LOTO	Lock out Tag out
OSHA	Occupational Safety and Health Administration

2.4.2 Definitions

2.4.2.1 Energy Isolating Device

These devices help ensure that energy isolation points are secure.

- Electrical lockout devices are used to help secure the electrical power of equipment in an “off” position.
- Multi-purpose cable lockout devices are commonly used for the lockout of several energy isolation points.
- Valve lockout devices are used to conceal or physically prevent the operation of valves.

Energy isolating devices DO NOT INCLUDE push buttons, selector switches, and other control circuit type devices.

2.4.2.2 Lockout Device

A lockout device is a device that utilizes a positive means to hold an energy isolating device in a safe position and prevents the energization of equipment and machinery. Examples of lockout devices are padlocks, blank flanges, and bolted slip blinds.

Padlocks

In contrast to ordinary padlocks, these must be issued and standardized by the employer. They must only be used for lockout purposes and are distinguishable from all other types of padlocks in the workplace. Key-retaining padlocks are best for lockout purposes to ensure that the padlock is locked before the key can be removed.

A LOTO padlock should only have one key. Lockout locks should not be keyed alike, in which multiple padlocks can be opened with one key. If the use of keyed alike locks cannot be avoided, limit their distribution among employees.

Figure 13: Lockout device.

Lockout hasp

The occasion may arise when multiple people need blocking the same source of energy, at the same time, such as during maintenance operations, where multiple individuals are engaged with the same machine, and therefore, all workers are required to maintain the equipment depowered and turned off.

However, the blocking method may only require, or indeed only accommodate, one padlock blocking it at any given time.

Hasps attempt to solve this issue by operating as a singular padlock, capable of blocking like any other regular padlock, with the different that lockout hasps are not locked by use of a key. Instead, they allow for the placement of multiple padlocks, who in turn assure that the hasp remains locked, allowing for multiple workers to block the same energy source.

Figure 14: Lockout Hasp.

Circuit Breaker Lockout

There are many different circuit breakers and electrical appliances, leading to many different types of circuit breaker lockouts. In general, these devices serve to keep the switch from moving, either by blocking the switch's movement, or covering the switch to block any interaction.

Figure 15: Circuit breaker lockout.

2.4.2.3 Tagout Device

A tagout device is a prominent warning device that can be securely fastened to an energy isolating device and indicates that both the equipment and the energy isolating device cannot be operated.

Tags

Tags are vital because they act as warnings against potential hazardous conditions when equipment or machines are energized. They provide vital information on the lockout condition of equipment in maintenance and can even contain a photo of the one responsible for specific equipment.

Company-issued tags should be standardized and distinguishable from other tags, include instructions and warnings, be able to withstand the environment they are in, and be attached with a self-locking non-reusable device that can withstand at least 50 pounds of pull force.

Figure 16: Tagout device.

LOTO Box

Also known as a lockbox or a group lockout box, a LOTO box is used when equipment has several isolation points that need to be secured (with their own energy isolating, lockout, and tagout devices) before it can be locked out. This is referred to as a group lockout or a group isolation.

Figure 17: LOTO box.

2.4.3 Roles and Responsibilities

2.4.3.1 Site Manager

The Site Manager shall ensure:

- a) Act as the lead “Issuing Authority” of the ISOLATION for all activities that are to be done inside allocated areas/systems
- b) Ensure that the precautions and conditions that are mentioned in an Isolation Plan are provided and maintained during the active lifetime of the Isolation Permit.
- c) In case the Site Manager is the also Construction Manager the Site Manager roles will also be applicable.
- d) Trained and competent personnel are provided to ensure that activities covered by this procedure are undertaken safely and effectively.
- e) All associated hazards are strictly controlled in line with risk assessments/method statements and permit requirements.
- f) Immediate reporting any issues to ensure timely correction.

2.4.3.2 Pre-commissioning Manager

The (pre) Commissioning Manager shall ensure.

They act as lead “Issuing Authority” of the ISOLATION for all activities that are to be executed inside Plant Systems and are owned by the Pre-Commissioning department.

The precautions and conditions that are mentioned in an Isolation Plan are provided and maintained during the active lifetime of the Isolation Permit.

2.4.3.3 Issuing Authority

The Issuing Authority shall ensure:

- a) Reviews are carried out on each request for an Isolation Permit for activities within those parts of the Plant owned by his discipline (Construction or Pre-Commissioning).
- b) They review content of the method statement, the risk assessment and the content of the Isolation Plan and Isolation Permit and accept, accept with comments or rejects the permit being request.
- c) They review content of proposed modifications to the Isolation Plan and/or the actual (emergency) removal of LOTO related equipment and accept, accept with comments, or reject the permit being request.
- d) They understand their actual responsibility for the specified activities and precautions and signs off acknowledgement on the permits.

2.4.3.4 Authorized Engineering (Electrical/Mechanical)

- a) Develop an Isolation Plan, based on the method statement of the related job activities in the Isolation Permit request (with special emphasis on any interlocks, back feeds or temporary energy sources).
- b) Anticipate on request for changes of Isolation plan by Authorized Operator or Holder (in case the job cannot be done within the present conditions of the Isolation plan.) by proposal of modification of the approved Isolation Plan.

2.4.3.5 System Owner (Authorized Operator Construction, (pre) Commissioning, Client)

- a) Secure a safe system by implementing the defined Isolation Plan.
- b) Secure a safe removal of an installed Isolation Plan after completion of all related activities.
- c) Close out the Isolation Permit according the PTW-process.

2.4.4 Standard Isolation for Hazard Control of Work

2.4.4.1 Preparation Stage

The applicant of a request to work that needs Isolation of a defined part of the installation makes a request towards the owner of that installation. At first an authorised engineer (appointed by the System Owner) will develop an "Isolation Plan" that must be accepted by the Issuing Authority.

After acceptance of the Isolation Plan the Authorised Engineer will make a PTW for the actual work-out of the Isolation and present the Isolation PTW package for acceptance by the Issuing Authority.

2.4.4.2 Requirements for an Isolation Plan

An Isolation plan is required for defined working activities inside a part of the installation that under normal conditions contain energy that could cause a risk of Injury to an Individual, a risk of Fire or Explosion, an Environmental risk or an Off-Site risk.

Examples of hazardous energy systems include, but are not limited to:

- a) Electricity (currents or static).
- b) Compressed fluids (especially Gasses in Pipes and vessels).
- c) Toxic, corrosive and/or flammable substances.
- d) Fluids or gasses which temperature is exceeding 60 degrees Celsius.

2.4.4.3 Isolation Plan Content

An Isolation Plan contains the following elements:

- a) Provide a list of energy systems within the area to be isolated, (based on Risk Assessment) such as:
 - Electrical, mechanical, chemical, thermal, or other energy sources whether active, stored or residual, that if not controlled, could cause injury to personnel.
 - Introduction of energy during job activities, such as chemical cleaning, pneumatic or electrical testing of equipment
- b) Specify methods for securing the installations (via method statements), such as:
 - Specific procedural steps for shutting down, isolating, blocking, and securing the system to be isolated.
 - Specific procedural steps for placing, removing, and transferring Isolation tools and devices and responsibilities for those steps.
 - Specific procedural steps for testing the isolated system to determine and verify the effectiveness of the Isolation Plan.
- c) Documenting of physical Isolation actions and conditions, such as:
 - LOTO action register for LOTO tools to be used.
 - Formal installation Drawings (P&ID / Engineering/ Equipment arrangement/ Underground etc) with the locations of LOTO marked on it.
 - Material Safety Data Sheet(s) (MSDS) when chemicals are involved.

2.4.4.4 Applicable Isolation Tools and Devices

For System Isolation only mechanical devices must be used to prevent the transmission or release of energy or material, such as:

- a) Uniquely numbered Padlocks and Lock boxes.
- b) All Padlocks are provided by the System Owner. Padlocks will be used for System Isolation and Personal Isolation by the Owner, Client, and other operatives:

- Lock boxes may be used for system isolation when there are numerous system locks, or many workers involved. The Lock box contains the keys of all defined system isolation locks. The Lock box is locked with a Lock-out Hasp and additional Padlock. The key to that padlock stays with the System Owner until all operators have finished their activity.
- c) LOTO Tags:
- A “Danger, do not operate” Tag is the Information carrier for an installed Padlock, spade, blind flange or Lock-Box. Such a Tag shall never be used as a standalone locking device! The placement of a single Tag means that an additional action of prevention must be defined and implemented further upstream towards the energy source.
 - A “Caution, Restricted Operation” Tag is used to inform about preferred status of the tagged device. It controls the methods personnel may use to operate, energize, or pressure a part of the Isolated Area. (Like testing of equipment with temporary energy sources or chemical cleaning.)
- d) Multi Locking Devices or Lockout Hasp:
- A Lockout Hasp is used to attach multiple padlocks at an isolation location.
 - The first hole contains the system Isolation Padlock; other holes may be used for Personal Isolation up to the last hole: that can be used for an additional Lockout Hasp, together with the next personal lock.
- e) Manual electrical disconnects.
- Fixate switches or other electrical devices in the OFF position.

Devices, such as switches, circuit breakers, push buttons, control- or solenoid valves that can be repositioned accidentally may not be used as isolating devices unless an additional device is used to ensure control (i.e. A lockable cap around a switch).

2.4.4.5 Duration of the Isolation Permit

An Isolation Permit will be validated for the duration that the SYSTEM ISOLATION is in place without adjustments to LOTO-actions at connections of the incoming energy sources (Boundaries).

2.4.4.6 Change of System Isolation Conditions

The change of System LOTO actions at the System Boundaries is NEVER allowed within an open Isolation Permit.

The System LOTO actions INSIDE an isolated system may be altered when different working activities requires so. The altered LOTO configuration and the methods how to change must be pre-defined in the original Isolation Plan that is issued by the Issuing Authority.

All changes must be noted in the LOTO Action Register, and all involved workers have to be informed that a change of the Isolation configuration will be performed.

No other Changes are allowed: A new Isolation Permit must be issued.

2.4.4.7 Emergency Removal of Personal LOTO Devices

Normally only the person who installed his personal LOTO device(s) also removes it.

If any lock cannot be removed using normal procedures, the Authorized Operator shall assemble a group, including management of the Owner and the involved contractor and related experts (such as an Authorized Electrical Engineer) and complete the following procedure:

- Verify that the person whose lock must be removed is not at the facility.
- Attempt to reach the person by all reasonable means.
- Inspect Equipment to ensure that it is safe to remove the LOTO device.
- Remove the device and record in the LOTO action Register.

Notify the person of the device of the removal before he returns to work.

2.4.4.8 Implementation Stage

The Authorised Operator receives the Isolation Permit Package and implements the steps of the Isolation Plan. The authorised Operator signs off his LOTO-actions in the LOTO action register.

2.4.4.9 ISOLATION during Working Activity

The permit Holder supervises the activities and the conditions around those activities. Regarding system isolation, the permit holder has the following duties:

- a) Confirms and secures the Isolation status by attaching his Padlocks either on a Lock Box-Lockout Hasp (when it is made available by the Owner) or every padlocked location of the Isolation Plan. He may leave his devices during time-off until the planned activity is done. Record his LOTO actions at the LOTO- Register attached to the PTW file.
- b) Ensures each worker attaches his personal padlocks at the Lock Box, or at the actual locations around his specific working area DURING THE TIME THEY ARE WORKING AT THE SYSTEM. They must remove their Padlock at the end of their shift. Record the LOTO actions at the LOTO Personal log sheet.
- c) Ensures all Isolation Actions by his party are removed and the LOTO-Personal log sheet is completed and handed over.

2.4.4.10 Termination of System Isolation

When all Holders with a related PTW reported the closure of their Personal actions, the Issuing Authority submits the Isolation permit to the Authorised operator for review of the installations and correction of irregular situations.

When the review shows that all work is finished, the Authorised Operator may start to remove the SYSTEM Isolation according to the Isolation Plan.

During the termination of the System Isolation the authorised Operator keeps track of his actions in the LOTO action register.

After completion of the Isolation plan the Authorised Operator request closure of the Isolation Permit of the Issuing Authority. After the acceptance of the Issuing Authority the Isolation Permit will be closed and archived by the Permit Coordinator.

2.4.4.11 Change Control of Standard Isolation for Hazard Control of Installations

The Owner can decide to install a project wide isolation at the boundaries of the Project or at the boundaries of a specific unit within the Project for specific energy sources for protection of all installations or a part of it.

The applicant for such an Isolation Permit is the Construction Manager or his designee, or the Senior Authorized Electrical Engineer.

2.4.4.12 Training

Maintain a training program that meets the following requirements:

- a) Train all employees exposed to sources of hazardous energy to a degree warranted by their job assignments in relation to the content of this procedure, which includes mandatory PTW and LOTO training.
- b) Register all training activities (Name, job title, date and company, course name) and archive those records in the HSE administration.

2.4.4.13 Audits

Conduct an audit procedure at least once every 6 months (depending on project duration) and within one year to ensure compliance with Legislation and Corporate rules, as well as to review the operational follow-up of the procedure by the workforce.

3 IMPLEMENTATION CHALLENGES

Taking this change into account, the main challenges for implementing the procedures presented in this study are the following:

1. Human factor Engineering

As Human Factors and Ergonomics (HFE) is a “sociotechnical” approach **to systems design**, it is necessary for the study to be carried out in a multidisciplinary environment with the involvement of organizations from each demo, considering the following factors that will influence the development of the project and its implementation:

- **People:** The characteristics, capabilities, expectations, limitations, experiences and needs of the people who will operate, maintain, support, and use the facilities.
- **Work:** The nature of the work involved in operating, maintaining, and supporting the facility.
- **Work Organization:** How the people are organized, in terms of, for example, team structures, responsibilities, working hours and Shift schedules.
- **Equipment:** The equipment and technology used, including the way equipment is laid out, and the elements that people need to interact with, both physically and mentally.
- **Environment:** The work environment in which people are expected to work, including the climate, lighting, noise, vibration, and exposure to other health hazards.

2. Design Safety

As this procedure defines and establishes the minimum requirements for the design and engineering of the safety systems required to eliminate, prevent, control or mitigate hazards associated with the electrification of ceramic industries at the three pilot sites (Torrecid, METLEN and IZF). It is necessary that the installation design, related to the materials, equipment, technologies and operations necessary to use the equipment as well as the work to be carried out to make the changes, are analyzed in the design phase from the perspective of health and safety, identifying all risks and preventive engineering measures necessary to meet safety and health objectives.

Safety in design is managed through a process of staged design and constructability reviews that become increasingly more fine-grained. For example, H&S risks should be analyzed in more detail as the design work progresses. Typically:

- a risk assessment protocol is established at the proposal development stage.
- a preliminary risk review is undertaken, and a risk register is established, at the concept design stage.

- further and progressively more detailed safety-in-design reviews occur at the concept and detailed design stages, and
- a final review of design-related H&S risks takes place at the construction document development stage (when detailed design is ‘frozen’).

This systematic approach to managing safety-in-design, undoubtedly increases the consistency and reliability of safety in design activities when applied across projects.

There is widespread recognition that safety-in-design reviews must involve people with knowledge and experience in the construction and maintenance of the facilities being designed.

In this context, integrating mechanisms are needed to ensure that communication flows are free and open, and that people with the correct mix of knowledge and experience are engaged in safety-in-design reviews.

3. PTW system

The efficacy of Permit-to-Work (PTW) systems is critical for maintaining safety in high-risk environments.

However, these systems often fall short due to various factors. A closer look at common PTW failures reveals a pattern: gaps in implementation, training, communication, and organizational culture can undermine the safety they are designed to ensure.

The warning signs that point towards PTW system failure, are the following:

- Inefficient Permit Preparation Timing
- Inadequate Hazard Coverage
- Lack of Automated Permit Procedure and Workflow
- Inability to Easily Copy and Adapt Permits
- Legibility Issues with Permits
- Permits’ Failure to Address Simultaneous Operations (SIMOPs)
- Insufficient Inspection Before & After Permit Signing
- Non-compliance with Permit Requirements by Workers
- Lack of Enforcement and Audit of the Permit-to-Work Process.

4. LOTO system

Implementing preventive safety measures, such as lockout tagout, is one of the most common and effective strategies to ensure workforce safety in the face of potential hazards and risks.

But even then, lockout tagout procedures only succeed if followed and implemented properly and effectively.

The **common challenges** in lockout tagout implementation, are the following:

- **Inadequate training and human negligence** - Employee training in lockout tagout procedures is crucial to its effective implementation.
- **Poor communication and documentation** – Personnel responsible for LOTO procedures should be able to effectively communicate their activity to fellow workers, supervisors, and other concerned employees.
- **Resistance to innovations and new safety technologies** – one of the challenges in the implementation of lockout tagout procedures involves the resistance of some industries to adopt innovations and technologies.
- **Build a rigid LOTO standard procedure** – it is critical to establish a standard procedure for LOTO operations that personnel will religiously know and follow. A rigid LOTO procedure should be able to identify roles and responsibilities including authorized and affected employees, and emphasize the importance of each step, from lockout, tagout, and documentation, to ensure safe and proper implementation during hazardous energy control.
- **Conduct regular audits and inspections** – To stay up to date, consider conducting more frequent audits and inspections of each LOTO procedure and employee training program.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The objective of changing heating processes in the ceramic industry pilot plant facilities (Torrecid, METLEN and IZF), replacing fossil energy sources (gas) for renewable energy sources using electrical energy, results in significant technological changes, whether related to the material resources necessary to carry out this change (electrical cables, electrical panels or furnace heating system) as well the associated technologies (electrical equipment, control systems), or also to the changes to be made to existing installations.

In terms of health and safety, it must be clear that the **risk level of the plant**, after changing to electrical energy sources, **should be lower**, considering the elimination of 2 major risk factors:

- Absence of gas (risk of fire and explosion);
- Reduction in complexity and frequency of maintenance tasks associated with cleaner technology.

To respond to this deliverable, “D2.5 – Implementation of Identified Health & Safety Requirements”, the first activity was to conduct a Gap analysis to identify areas where current processes and products do not meet health and safety requirements, considering the specific challenges of the electrification process, such as electrical hazards, fire hazards, temperature hazards and chemical exposure.

The Referred Gap Analysis was based on the preparation of a health and safety requirements checklist (Annex 5.1.) resulting from a risk analysis of a kiln, distributed to all Demos Sites.

In the receiving responses, the only identified GAPS were the absence of two organizational preventive measures, namely, **PTW (Permit to Work Procedure) and LOTO (Lock-Out TAG-Out) procedures**.

Beyond this first phase, taking into account that the **development of the projects** of each pilot site, will only be developed in the next 2 years and therefore there is not enough data on the final equipment at this stage, the task of SGS - Implementation of Identified Health & Safety Requirements, will continue in this development, and its contribution to the application of the following procedures is essential, which are part of this deliverable:

1. **Design Safety Philosophy** – This document defines and establishes the minimum requirements for the design and engineering of the safety systems required to eliminate, prevent, control or mitigate the plant hazards;

- 2. Human Factor Engineering (HFE) Philosophy** – This document defines the principles focus on respecting the individual and social integrity of workers, on creating safe and healthy workspaces.

This contribution will be put into practice in joint working sessions with WP4 – WP6, which will encompass the development and prototyping of the overall lay-out and elements related to the three electric furnaces technologies; (WP4) the ceramic frits smelter, (WP5) the alumina calciner and (WP6) the brick firing, including new materials formulations and the power-to-heat supply systems (i.e. induction, microwave and radiant walls). In these working sessions, SGS's contribution will be based on a H&S risk analysis of each solution.

That H&S risks should be analyzed in more detail as the design work progresses and further and progressively more detailed safety-in-design reviews occur at the concept and detailed design stages, and a final review of design-related H&S risks takes place at the construction document development stage (when detailed design is 'frozen').

Beyond this project development phase, SGS's task will continue **in the implementation phase** with all these work packages (W4-W6), which will consider a final engineering stage to integrate the solutions in the current processes, commissioning and demonstration campaigns in real industrial sites.

This will ensure the implementation of the two applicable procedures for the commissioning and testing phase, presented in this deliverable:

- 3. Permit to Work (PTW) Procedure** – A permit to work can be considered as a specialised Safe System of Work under which certain high risk activities may only be carried out with specific permission of the Authorised Person;
- 4. Lock-Out /TAG-Out (LOTO) Procedure** – this is a specific procedure to prevent the unexpected energization, start-up or release of stored energy that may result in bodily injury or property damage during construction, testing, maintenance and servicing of machinery or equipment by ISOLATION (Lockout/Tag out (LOTO) of that part of the installations that is related to a specified hazardous job activity.

With this finally stage of SGS` s contribution, it will be ensured that the identified health and safety requirements are implemented and enforced throughout the process, considering regular inspections and training sessions that can help maintain compliance and prevent accidents. This will create inputs for the developments WP4-WP6 and WP7.

5 ANNEXES

5.1 Safety Requirements Table Checklist

HEALTH AND SAFETY RISKS VS. CONTROL MEASURES (SAFETY REQUIREMENTS)
ACTIVITY and/or ENVIRONMENT TO BE ASSESSED: Use of Kiln

KEY (People at risk)
 E = Employee; P = Public ; C = Contractors;
 V = Visitors

1.Hazards Identified and potential harm it could cause	2. People At Risk	3.Controls in Place (SAFETY REQUIREMENTS)	YES	NO
Heat Metal casing of kiln/firing objects		• Hot materials handled with tongs or other suitable tools.		
		• Safety Gloves to be worn when removing items whilst kiln still warm		
		• Kilns situated in working areas should be caged/isolated		
		• PPE Plan;		
		• Handling procedure		
Fire		• Detailed Fire Risk Assessment conducted and reviewed annually		
		• Flammable materials are not to be stored in the kiln room.		
		• Clear circulation space is maintained at all times (450mm).		
		• Appropriate fire extinguisher present in vicinity;		
		• Automatic fire extinguishing system (sprinklers, another,..)		
Electrocution Electrical shock Burns		• No access to live heating elements - interlocking device where the kiln door cannot be		

<p>Contact with moving parts during testing, inspection, maintenance, cleaning, or repair.</p> <p>Lack of oxygen and Atmospheric contamination inside the Kiln during testing, inspection, maintenance, cleaning, or repair;</p>		opened before the mains supply is switched off.		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Installed by a competent electrician. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accessible and labelled isolation point. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extension leads / multiway plugs not to be used to connect kiln. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Visual inspection conducted pre-use. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kiln must be regularly inspected by a competent person; 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lock Out – Tag Out (LOTO) procedure 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Permit to Work (PTW) Procedure 		
Use of ceramic materials		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less hazardous chemicals used wherever possible. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No food or drink to be prepared or consumed in any area used for pottery. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective hand washing after using ceramics materials and chemicals. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All materials are properly labelled and stored, and appropriate warnings are included in the labelling. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Material Safety Data Sheet for substances obtained from supplier and guidance followed. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Control of Substances Hazardous to Health Assessment completed for all hazardous chemicals and control measures implemented. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Immediate cleaning up of any spillage 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuous oxygen measure inside the kiln. Procedure for work in Confined spaces 		

Non authorised use		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used only by competent operators 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kiln sited in a lockable, specialist room which has an external red warning light / warning system. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Written procedures on safe use and emergency procedures posted next to kiln. 		
Ceramic lining/asbestos lining (Ingestion of toxic substances, skin irritation/ sensitization)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check Site asbestos log information for location of asbestos containing material. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular monitoring to ensure that the asbestos is not damaged. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specialist advice to be sought if work planned on a kiln which could disturb asbestos. 		
Inhalation of dusts including pottery glazes causing harm to health.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cleaning routines used limit the generation of dusts. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dry materials stored in sealed containers, spillages cleaned up immediately. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Area regularly cleaned to prevent build-up of clay dust. Floors wet moped daily. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tables and surfaces to be cleaned whilst clay is damp. 		
Fumes Irritation/sensitisation to respiratory tract		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Good natural ventilation e.g. through doors /windows or extraction fan 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do not used lead-based glazes. 		
Glazes to be used with foodstuffs (Ingestion of toxic /harmful substances)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do not use lead-based glazes. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure glazes or colour do not release metallic compounds when they come into contact with acids contained in food stuffs. 		

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure glazes are used in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. 		
Spray application glazes (Irritation/sensitisation to respiratory tract)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spray glazes should only be used in properly designed spray booth or in outside areas. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operator should wear a mask. 		
Slips/Trips		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure good housekeeping in the kiln room. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide wet floor signs when floor is moped. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dry mop floors after spillages. 		
Manual handling loading / unloading ware		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workers should normally load kilns. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workers with adequate training and supervised and correct procedures for manual loading and unloading. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Appropriate footwear worn 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mechanical lifting aids available (trolleys etc.) 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heavy items stored at waist level. 		

5.2 Table of Permit to Work System Templates

Doc No.	Document Name	File Type	HSE Filing Section
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Permit System Templates			
PTW_ELITHE.01	General Work Permit		
PTW_ELITHE.02	Hot Work Permit		
PTW_ELITHE.03	Permit to Carry Out Electrical Functional Testing		
PTW_ELITHE.04	Electrical Permit to Work		
PTW_ELITHE.05	Confined Space Work Permit		

4.2.1 PTW_ELITHE.01 - General Work Permit

		GENERAL WORK PERMIT			PERMIT No.: 0
1. NAME OF CONTRACTOR:					CROSS REF:
2. AREA:					
3. DETAILS OF WORK TO BE CARRIED OUT:					
4. RA / MS No.					
5. TOOLS/EQUIPMENT TO BE USED (HAND / AIR / BATTERY ETC):					
6. PLANT / EQUIPMENT ISOLATIONS	YES	NO	SPECIFY METHODS		SIGNATURE
ELECTRICAL (See note 2)					
MECHANICAL					
PROCESS					
OTHER (specify)					
7. PRECAUTIONS REQUIRED:			COMMENT:		
RESIDUAL HAZARDS: (NOT COVERED BY RISK ASSESSMENT / METHOD STATEMENT):			COMMENT:		
8. AUTHORISATION BY ISSUER :					
All the precautions listed in section 7 have been taken, the work area has been inspected and I authorise work to start.					
ISSUER (PRINT NAME):		SIGNATURE:		DATE/TIME:	
9. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT BY ACCEPTOR :					
I have read and fully understood the conditions of this Permit. These will be fully explained to those working under my control who will sign the Working Party Declaration on the reverse side of this Permit. I accept responsibility for ensuring that they follow the conditions of the Permit.					
ACCEPTOR (PRINT NAME):		SIGNATURE:		DATE/TIME:	
10. CANCELLATION BY ACCEPTOR :					
I declare that the work has been completed, that all tools and equipment have been removed and the work area restored to a safe condition.					
ACCEPTOR (PRINT NAME):		SIGNATURE:		DATE/TIME:	
11. ACCEPTANCE OF WORK AREA BACK BY ISSUER :					
I can confirm that the work area has been inspected and that the above clearance has been satisfactorily carried out. This Permit is now cancelled.					
ISSUER (PRINT NAME):		SIGNATURE:		DATE/TIME:	
Distribution: White copy – Displayed in work area, Pink copy – Retained by Permit Office.					
Note 1: This Permit is automatically suspended upon emergency alarms sounding. Please check with the Permit Co-ordinator / Issuer before recommencing work.					
Note 2: Electrical isolations shall only be undertaken by a person holding a written authorisation from the Company's Senior Authorised Person.					

4.2.2. PTW_ELITHE.02 - Hot Work Permit

		HOT WORK PERMIT		PERMIT No.:
1. NAME OF CONTRACTOR:				CROSS REF:
2. AREA:				
3. DETAILS OF WORK TO BE CARRIED OUT:				
4. RA / MS No.				
6. TOOLS/EQUIPMENT TO BE USED (HAND / AIR / ELECTRICAL ETC)				
6. PRECAUTIONS REQUIRED :		COMMENT:		
RESIDUAL HAZARDS: (NOT COVERED BY RISK ASSESSMENT / METHOD STATEMENT):		OTHER NECESSARY PRECAUTIONS: PROTECTIVE CLOTHING OR EQUIPMENT REQUIRED:		
7. ARTLANT/CONTRACTOR INTERFACE AWARENESS:				
I have read and fully understood the conditions of this Permit and am aware of the activities taking place.				
<u>WORK AWARENESS</u>		<u>WORK COMPLETION</u>		
NAME & SIGNATURE:		NAME & SIGNATURE:		
DATE / TIME:		DATE / TIME:		
8. PERMIT VALID FROM:		PERMIT VALID TO:		
DATE:	TIME:	DATE:	TIME:	
10. AUTHORISATION BY ISSUER :		11. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT BY ACCEPTOR :		
All the precautions listed in section 6 have been taken, the work area has been inspected by a Permit Issuer and I authorise work to start.		I have read and fully understood the conditions of this Permit. These have also been fully explained to the operatives who will carry out the work. I accept responsibility for ensuring that they follow their instructions.		
ISSUER	(PRINT NAME):	ACCEPTOR	(PRINT NAME):	
SIGNATURE:		SIGNATURE:		
SIGNATURE:		SIGNATURE:		
DATE/TIME:		DATE/TIME:		
		DATE/TIME:		
		DATE/TIME:		
		DATE/TIME:		

<p>12. CANCELLATION BY ACCEPTOR:</p>	<p>13. ACCEPTANCE OF WORK AREA BACK BY ISSUER:</p>
<p>I declare that the work has been completed, that all tools and equipment have been removed and the work area restored to a safe condition. PRINT NAME: SIGNATURE: DATE/TIME:</p>	<p>I can confirm that the work area has been inspected by a Permit Issuer and that the above clearance has been satisfactorily carried out. This Permit is now cancelled. PRINT NAME: SIGNATURE: DATE/TIME: DATE/TIME:</p>
<p>Distribution: White copy – Displayed in work area, Pink copy – Retained by Permit Issuer.</p>	
<p>Note 1: This Permit is automatically suspended upon emergency alarms sounding. Please check with the Permit Issuer before recommencing work.</p>	

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4.2.4. PTW_ELITHE.04 - Electrical Permit to Work

	ELECTRICAL PERMIT TO WORK	PERMIT No.:
COPY 1 – RECIPIENT COPY 2 – EQUIPMENT ATTACHMENT COPY 3 – PERMIT OFFICE FILE / RETAINED IN BOOK		
<u>1. ISSUE</u>		
Project No: TO	Project Name: In the employment of.....	
I hereby declare that it is safe to work on the following equipment, which is dead, isolated from all live conductors and is connected to earth. <i>Declaro que é seguro para trabalhar com os seguintes equipamentos, que está desligado, isolado de todos os condutores vivos e está ligado à terra.</i>		
<u>ALL OTHER EQUIPMENT IS DANGEROUS</u>		
Points of Isolation		
Points of Earth Connection (for High Voltage equipment)		
Other Precautions		
The following work is to be carried out		
Issued By		
Name:	Signature:	Date:
Time:		
Being an Authorised Person* (for LV Permits only) or Senior Authorised Person* appointed to issue an Electrical Permit to Work.		
<u>2. RECEIPT</u>		
I hereby declare that I accept responsibility for carrying out the work on the equipment detailed on this Permit to Work and that no attempt will be made by me, or by the persons under my control, to carry out work on any other equipment.		
Name:	Signature:	Date:
Time:		
Note: After signature for the work to proceed this receipt must be signed by and the Permit to Work be retained by the person in charge of the work until the work is suspended or completed and the clearance section has been signed.		
<u>3. CLEARANCE</u>		
I hereby declare that the work for which this Permit to Work was issued is now *suspended/completed, and that all workers under my charge have been withdrawn and warned that it is no longer safe to work on the equipment specified on this Permit to Work, and that gear, tools and additional earthing connections are clear of the designated equipment.		
Name:	Signature:	Date:
Time:		

<u>4. CANCELLATION</u>			
Name:	Signature:	Date:	Time:
Being an Authorised Person* (for LV Permits only) or Senior Authorised Person* appointed to cancel an Electrical Permit to Work.			

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the European Union.

<p>16. CANCELLATION BY ACCEPTOR:</p> <p>I declare that the work has been completed / stopped, that all tools and equipment have been removed and the work area restored to a safe condition.</p> <p>PRINT NAME: SIGNATURE: DATE/TIME:</p>	<p>17. ACCEPTANCE OF WORK AREA BACK BY ISSUER:</p> <p>I can confirm that the work area has been inspected by a Permit Issuer and that the above clearance has been satisfactorily carried out. This Permit is now cancelled.</p> <p>PRINT NAME: SIGNATURE: DATE/TIME:</p> <p>DATE/TIME:</p>
<p>Distribution: White copy – Displayed in work area, Pink copy – Retained by Permit Issuer.</p>	
<p>Note 1: This Permit is automatically suspended upon emergency alarms sounding. Please check with the Permit Issuer before recommencing work.</p>	

5.3 Table of LOTO system templates

Doc No.	Document Name	File Type	HSE Filing Section
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LOTO System Templates			
LOTO_ELITHE.01	Form LOTO Action Register		

6.3.1. LOTO_ELITHE.01 - Form LOTO Action Register

		Please write in this column only			
PTW number:					
PTW Holder Name Company					
Scope of work:					
Equipment Description:					
System and Area:					
LOCK BOX			IF NO LOCKBOX available: Do LOTO according System Isolation Plan:		
Craft / Contractor:	System Lock	Craft Person Signature:	Lock Placed On Lock Box: Date and Time:	Lock Removed From Lock Box: Date and Time:	Release Signature(s):
DATE RECONCILED:					

6 REFERENCES

Council Directive 92/57/EEC of 24 June 1992 on the implementation of minimum safety and health requirements at temporary or mobile construction sites (eighth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 (1) of Directive 89/391/EEC)

Directive 2006/42/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 May 2006 on machinery, and amending Directive 95/16/EC (recast)

European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions (1991). From Drawing Board to Building Site. Luxemburg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities

EN 547-3:1996+A1:2008 Safety of machinery - Human body measurements Part 3. Anthropometric data

GAP.2.5.2.A: Hazard Classification for Process Operations for Spacing Requirements

<https://www.juliantalbot.com/post/2017/06/13/as-low-as-reasonably-practicable-alarp>

ISO 11064 Ergonomic design of control centres

NFPA 70: National Electrical Code

PNE00003: Process Unit and Offsites Layout Guide

Report 454 Human factors engineering in projects by IOGP and Energy Institute (EI);

Reason, J. (1997) Managing the Risks of Organizational Accidents. Ashgate, London;

The OSHA standard for The Control of Hazardous Energy (Lockout/Tagout), Title 29 Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) Part 1910.147 and 29 CFR 1910.333

